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Document Overview

1. Objectives and Team

The Ministero dell'Università e della Ricerca (MUR) has concluded a Grant Agreement (GA) with the ITSERR consortium (ITSERR)¹ for the provision of IT services to support the existing national infrastructure and bring it to a higher level of maturity, in terms of involvement of technology and ability to increase the innovation, quality and variety of the knowledge produced by the community of Religious Studies.

Within the structure of the ITSERR project, the Work Package 8 (WP8)–*uBIQUity*, which incorporates the “BI” of the Bible(s) and the “QU” of the Quran in its title, aims at investigating the sacred texts of Christianity and Islam in different environments and historical periods through two huge *corpora*: Greek and Latin Christian commentaries on the Bible(s) written from the Patristic age until the Late Byzantine period, and classical commentaries on the Quran written in Arabic (*tafāsīr*) from the rise of Islam until the 15th century.

These works are unique sources for the study of knowledge, readings, and hermeneutics of the sacred texts through the centuries. The intertextual references, conscious or unconscious, that the ancient commentaries contain work as invisible “places of memory”, thus making sacred texts “ubiquitous” (hence the title of the project). Indeed, these references, once placed in new contexts for new audiences and readers, become something other than themselves while continuing to refer to themselves and their source text, for those who can still grasp it.

This document is the first deliverable for *uBIQUity* (D8.1.1) and represents the reference document by which the WP8 team provides a comprehensive description of its efforts to examine and interconnect the above-mentioned *corpora*. This whitepaper details how *corpora* in different languages and alphabets have been prepared for processing, drawing on experience gained from studying and working with the Bible(s), the Quran, and their commentaries. It also describes the research carried out in the field of Computer Science to produce concordance lists indicating possible intertextual allusions.

The WP8 team members are:

Sara **ABRAM**, University of Palermo (UNIPA): Arabic texts.

Marcello **COSTA**, UNIPA: visual communication design.

¹ ITSERR is a consortium composed of National Research Council (CNR), University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE), University of Naples L'Orientale (UNIOR), University of Palermo (UNIPA), and University of Torino (UNITO).

Fabrizio **D'AVENIA**, WP8 Leader, UNIPA.

Cinzia **FERRARA**, UNIPA: visual communication design.

Anna **MAMBELLI**, WP8 Scientific Coordinator and Product Owner, University of Modena and Reggio Emilia (UNIMORE): Greek and Latin texts.

Chiara **PALILLO**, UNIPA: visual communication design.

Fabio **TUTRONE**, UNIPA: Latin texts.

Regarding research in the field of Computer Science, for the Latin section, the collaboration with the UNIMORE team composed of Davide **CAFFAGNI**, Federico **COCCHI**, Marcella **CORNIA**, Rita **CUCCHIARA**, and also with Cesare **CONCORDIA** and Carlo **MEGHINI** of the National Research Council (CNR) is fundamental. As for the Arabic section of WP8, Andrea **ESULI**, Giovanni **PUCCETTI**, and Fabrizio **SEBASTIANI** of the CNR are working on the IT side.

Concerning research and work on Ancient Greek, WP8 has decided to collaborate with the team of another project with similar aims, which has been incubated in the framework of RESILIENCE RI, namely the PRIN (Italian Research Project of National Interest, n. 20229E83B3) *Resilient Septuagint. An Initial Exploration of the Semantics of Killing and Healing in the Septuagint and its Reception in Patristic and Late Antique Sources (3rd cent. BCE-5th cent. CE)*. This PRIN project involves the *Alma Mater Studiorum* University of Bologna (UNIBO, PI Research Unit), the University of Bari (UNIBA), and the University of Catania (UNICT). The *Resilient Septuagint* team members are: Luca **ARCARI** (University of Naples Federico II), Laura **BIGONI** (UNIBO), Laura **CARNEVALE** (UNIBA Research Unit Chief), Davide **DAINESE** (PI, UNIBO), Isabella **PIGNOCCO** (UNICT), Arianna **ROTONDO** (UNICT Research Unit Chief and deputy PI), Giorgia **SAMPÒ** (DDC University of Southern Denmark-UNIBO), Gianluca **SCATIGNO** (UNIBO), Marco **ZANELLA** (University of Padua-UNIBO). This collaboration between WP8 and *Resilient Septuagint* has included and will continue to include the development of a shared methodological framework and interoperable datasets for the study of Greek biblical texts and their heritage.

2. Scope

Basically, there are three lines of research within *uBIQUity*:

a) The first is aimed at the history of receptions (strictly in the plural) and intends to combine some of the *tesserae* from the material and “mental” libraries of ancient authors to show part of the patristic complex literary mosaic of biblical allusions and reworkings, and the immense mosaic of Quranic and *aḥādīth* (the Sayings of the Prophet) quotations and reinterpretations in the *tafāsīr*.

What the project is interested in, however, is not pure literary and quantitative data. Rather, this research on shared “places of memory” (*lieux de mémoire*) focuses on reconstructing the “collective memories” of religious communities over time and space, for example through the creation of

semantic maps that show the oscillation of recurrent interpretations of sacred texts and the consequent shifting of religious identities within faith communities.

b) The second line of research concerns biblical sources. It is intended to illuminate obscure areas of the tradition of sacred texts by trying to unearth possible “submerged” *Vorlagen*. After all, if we consider that the *Veteres Latinae* were reconstructed largely by indirect tradition from quotations of the Latin Fathers, it is not impossible that the circular movement from the Bibles to the patristic texts and back, performed on an enormous quantity of machine-processed data, could bring to light biblical passages quoted by authors in a shared form. Obviously, these shared forms, if any significant ones emerge, must be investigated with all possible caution, since they may simply be due to the influence of one authoritative writer on others.

c) The third line of research focuses on the quotations and textual adaptations of the Sayings of the Prophet (*aḥādīth*) in Quranic commentaries (*tafāsīr*). This area of investigation opens up new avenues of research, offering the opportunity to analyze the various uses, purposes, and exegetical practices through which the words of the Prophet are integrated into this literature, with particular attention to the contexts in which they are employed and the Quranic verses they are associated with. The quantitative collection and qualitative analysis of these data, supported by computational tools, will provide deeper insights into the relationship between *tafāsīr* and another fundamental literary genre within the Islamic religious tradition, the one dedicated specifically to the preservation of the prophetic legacy, represented by both canonical and non-canonical collections of the Sayings of the Prophet. Although these are two distinct literary genres, they are deeply interconnected: *tafāsīr* draw extensively from the collections of *ḥādīth* while maintaining distinct purposes and formulations. Identifying the Sayings of the Prophet within the exegetical corpus represented by *tafāsīr* — where their wording may range from being identical to traditional collections to being similar or entirely different — will shed light on the interactions between these two literary traditions, as well as the degree of textual correlation and borrowing between the *tafāsīr* themselves. This will allow the reconstruction of the complex history of transmission and reinterpretation of the words of the Prophet within the religious texts of the Islamic tradition.

By interweaving Computer Science and the Humanities, *uBIQUity* aims to develop the prototype of a new research tool that can identify quotations/allusions to the Bible(s), the Quran, and the *aḥādīth* in Christian and Islamic ancient works with a higher degree of accuracy than pre-existing resources.

This software might have further applications in the research of intertextual references in different kinds of literary production: for example, within our field of interest, it may be applied to the research of extra-biblical influences within biblical texts or Greek philosophical influences in Arabic texts.

For the development of the prototype of this search engine, *uBIQUity* closely cooperates with the *Resilient Septuagint* team (see above, 1.) for the Greek Bible(s) and Patristic section and includes an investigation into generative AI strategies and tools to generate new knowledge on “biblical filigrees”, that is the ubiquitous presence, relevance, and reconfiguration of biblical references in the works and thought of Christian Greek authors. In particular, the PRIN *Resilient Septuagint* team has designed with the WP8 team and delivered to *uBIQUity* portions of a Greek tagset and dataset. The latter, called

EnGraSept (Enriched Granular Septuagint), is a metadata digital version of the edited text of the Greek Bible(s) (see below, 8.2). The former aims at describing the semantic similarity between Greek texts through an annotation system to be performed on the INCEpTION platform (see below, 6.). As a result of this joint collaborative effort, *uBIQUity* benefits from the parallel experimental activity carried out by the *Resilient Septuagint* team, which in turn gains an advantage in terms of research scope and impact. Both *uBIQUity* and *Resilient Septuagint* originate from the methodological framework of the *Historical and Theological Lexicon of the Septuagint* (edited by E. BONS and D. SCIALABBA, in collaboration with A. MAMBELLI, 4 vols., Mohr Siebeck, Tübingen 2020–), which also aims at considering the lexicon of the Septuagint Bible within the broader history of the Greek language, from the earliest attestations of a significant word up to its first reception in Christian authors.

3. Outreach

1. Collaboration of WP8 with the editors of *The Historical and Theological Lexicon of the Septuagint*, Eberhard Bons (University of Strasbourg) and Daniela Scialabba (Pontifical Biblical Institute in Rome): <https://www.fscire.it/school/the-historical-and-theological-lexicon-of-the-septuagint-htls>.
2. Monitoring of the results of the project *Linked Open Tafsir*, led by Ömer Özsoy (Goethe University's Academy for Islam in Science and Society AIWG in Frankfurt), Serdar Kurnaz (Humboldt University in Berlin), and Yaşar Sarıkaya (Justus Liebig University in Giessen): <https://aiwg.de/kurzbeschreibung-linked-open-tafsir/>.
3. Meeting and presentation with Tobias Nicklas and Erik Eynikel (University of Regensburg) from the research center *Beyond Canon* and the project *Novum Testamentum Patristicum Commentary Series*: <https://www.uni-regensburg.de/theology/novum-testamentum-patristicum/home/index.html> (Regensburg, December 15-16, 2022).
4. Recognition on the status of the *Tesserae Project* with Neil Coffee (University of Buffalo): <https://www.buffalo.edu/digital-scholarship-studio-network/projects/faculty-projects/tesserae.html> (online, September 2023).
5. Informal recognition on the status of the *Hexapla Project* with Beatrice Bonanno (Catholic University of Louvain): <https://textandcanon.org/research/hexapla/> (online, November 15, 2023).
6. Meeting with Felix Albrecht and Margherita Matera (Georg August University of Göttingen) on the latest project of the *Göttinger Septuaginta* and the possibility of collaboration: <https://septuaginta.uni-goettingen.de/> (Göttingen, January 8, 2024).
7. Meeting with Marco Büchler (InfAI) on *Tracer* and other software for research on intertextuality: <https://infai.org/> (Leipzig, January 12, 2024).
8. Meeting with Laurence Mellerin (HISOMA Lab) and the group working on *Sources Chrétiennes* and *BiblIndex*: <https://sourceschretiennes.org/> (Lyon, March 5, 2024).

9. Meetings and collaborative research with Chiara Zanchi (University of Pavia) and the team working on *Ancient Greek WordNet*: <https://greekwordnet.chs.harvard.edu/> (online and in person, from March 2024).
10. Meetings with Marco Passarotti (Catholic University of Milan) and the team working on *LiLa: Linking Latin*: <https://lila-erc.eu/> (online, from March 2024).
11. Exchange with Hugh Houghton (University of Birmingham) on the ongoing project of the *Vetus Latina Institute*: <https://www.herder.de/vetus-latina/> (online, from March 2024).
12. Meeting with Tuukka Kauhanen (University of Helsinki) and the team working for the *Centre of Excellence in Changes in Sacred Texts and Traditions*; <https://researchportal.helsinki.fi/en/projects/centre-of-excellence-in-changes-in-sacred-texts-and-traditions> (online, March 19, 2024).
13. Training with CLARIN on linguistic resources for the study of Ancient Greek, Latin, and Arabic: <https://www.clarin.eu/> (Reggio Emilia, June 10-11, 2024).
14. Participation to the meeting organized by the KITAB project, led by Sarah Bowen Savant (Institute for the Study of Muslim Civilizations, Aga Kahn University London), regarding the latest version (2023.1.8) of its platform, which includes digitized texts from the OpenITI corpus (Sarah Bowen Savant, Matthew Thomas Miller [University of Maryland, College Park] and Maxim G. Romanov [University of Vienna]: <https://openiti.org/>): <https://kitab-project.org/> (online, September 17, 2024).
15. Meeting with Ide François and Gert Partoens (KU Leuven) on the Latin Patristic tradition, particularly on the texts of Augustine (Leuven, October 2024).

4. State of the Art

The study of the technologies available to date for Graeco-Roman antiquity and for traditional and exegetical texts in Arabic has been the first crucial step of the work in *uBIQUity*. From the reconstruction of the *status quaestionis* carried out by the WP8 team, it is evident that significant efforts have been made, accelerated over the past 15 years, to provide scholars with an outstanding collection of literary and exegetical heritage. This also includes resources such as dictionaries and lexicons, translations, automatic lemmatization of inflected forms, N-grams, and concordances.

The problem concerning biblical sources, however, is that existing tools generally provide the reconstructed text of only one edition for each work and without a critical apparatus. Most of the tools, moreover, are only available with a paid subscription, which poses a compelling issue of accessibility. This scarcity (or in some cases lack) of digital sources in the case of Bibles has negative consequences that are more evident than with extra-biblical texts, both from a methodological and qualitative-scientific point of view. Indeed, the biblical tradition has always been intrinsically plural, with different versions of the same texts circulating among different communities over the centuries. The picture of a single text, be it the reproduction of a single manuscript or an eclectic edition, is not suitable for any historical, literary, or theological analysis. The tools we currently use only provide a

Bible in Greek (the Septuagint in Rahlfs-Hanhart' edition: see below, 5.1) and a Bible in Latin (the Vulgate in Weber-Gryson's edition: see below, 5.1), mostly stripped of their significant variant readings of apparatus. The only platforms that contain the full text of the apparatus of the Greek Septuagint Bible are *Accordance* (<https://www.accordancebible.com>) and *Logos* (<https://www.logos.com/>), which however, in addition to being chargeable, do not link the text to the corresponding variant readings, thus making the fruition of the tool far less convenient than the printed page of the edition.

This situation gives the erroneous impression that the Bible circulating in the ancient Graeco-Roman world was a single, monolithic text, and this sometimes pushes even the most motivated scholar to a harmful intellectual, philological, and exegetical laziness. For example, the quantity of results produced after posing a query from databases such as the *Thesaurus Linguae Graecae* (TLG) can give an illusion of knowledge. The quantitative illusion, however, has nothing to do with textual plurality, which also means exegetical plurality, of biblical texts. If the TLG gives us 1,000 results for occurrences of the term εἰρήνη ("peace") in the Greek Bible, but only within the Rahlfs-Hanhart' edition (see below, 5.1), we cannot claim to have real knowledge of the textual history and uses of that word. To date, the only tool available for finding biblical references in patristic works is *BiblIndex* (<https://www.biblindex.org/en>), which, however, has an evident limitation: it does not perform a direct search in the texts, but only relies on the biblical passages identified as such by the editors of each work and redirects to the pages and paragraphs of the printed editions.

It then becomes necessary to rely on new methodological paradigms as a solid basis for the creation of a search engine like *uBIQUity*, in order that as new needs arise, a technology is born that incorporates, digests, and yields knowledge in an expanded fashion. Technology can and must not be simplification. Therefore, *uBIQUity* aims to restore the complexity of the history of textual traditions by superimposing multiple ancient biblical versions and putting them into dialogue with the centuries-long tradition of exegetical commentaries.

On the Arabic-language literature side, there is also a significant challenge posed by the lack of advanced and specialized tools for identifying and analyzing text reuse and intertextuality in Islamic religious texts. There are no resources yet available that allow efficient analysis of intertextual references, such as tools for the automatic lemmatization of inflected forms, in-depth semantic analysis, N-grams, and concordances. This deficiency limits scholars' ability to accurately trace connections between *tafāsīr* and other literary traditions, such as collections of *ḥādīth*.

Moreover, as far as all the above-mentioned fields of research are concerned, even when resources useful for linguistic studies are available (such as digitized dictionaries and lexicons, translations, and morphological support tools), these tools are often fragmented and lack integration. The absence of a unified platform that combines these resources with advanced technologies for intertextual reference detection significantly hampers the efficiency and scope of research. An integrated solution offering tools for automatic lemmatization, linguistic and morphological support, and the identification of both literal and non-literal intertextual references would be a crucial step forward for

the advancement of studies and perhaps contribute to changing the perspective from which scholars look at those sources, inviting more debate and paving the way to fresh approaches. Such a platform would allow researchers to address the complexity of textual interactions within Arabic religious texts, providing more effective support and a deeper understanding of the Islamic exegetical tradition. The possibility of visualizing a large amount of data in a user-friendly platform that allows for different research paths would be extremely beneficial to the scholarly community of Religious Studies, enabling greater accessibility and inclusivity in the field, as well as promoting innovative perspectives and methodologies. This scope has guided the work of the WP8 team towards the establishment of a rigorous methodology for the identification and analysis of intertextual references as a basis for the creation of the semantic search engine.

5. Methodology

A methodologically sound approach to the multifaceted textual heritage of sacred texts and exegetical compilations described so far requires a full awareness of the existing digital *corpora*, which include the critically edited texts of the Bible(s) and the biblical commentaries on the one hand, and the Quran, the *ḥādīṭ* collections, and the *tafāsīr* on the other. A comprehensive survey of the available *corpora* was thus carried out in the first stages of WP8's work to assess the usefulness and completeness of the current resources, as well as to explore the most promising avenues for future research (see above, 4.). In what follows, we will first provide an overview of the resources available for our source texts – the Bible(s), the Quran, and the *ḥādīṭ* collections, which are the actual sources of the quotations and allusions that the WP8 team intends to track down. We will secondarily describe our findings and choices concerning the *corpora* of patristic commentaries and *tafāsīr*, which are the target texts hosting the above-mentioned intertextual references.

5.1 Source Texts

As for the Greek Bible, the three main traditions represented by the Septuagint (LXX), the Hexapla (H), and the New Testament (NT) have been found to be accessible in the critical editions and digital formats that we will report on below. However, some texts are available online but only in PDF format, as detailed below.

In addition, the critical apparatus is included in a digital edition exclusively for the Göttingen Septuagint, where both the critical apparatus and the Hexaplaric apparatus are accessible and can be viewed separately from the edited text on the *Logos* (<https://www.logos.com/>) and *Accordance* (<https://www.accordancebible.com>) platforms. However, these are proprietary services that require significant costs for access. WP8 has obtained through *Logos* the digital collection of volumes published to date, consisting of 24 volumes plus one supplement.

The *Göttingen Septuagint* (G_LXX: *Septuaginta: Vetus Testamentum Graecum auctoritate Academiae Scientiarum Gottingensis editum*) serves as the primary reference edition of the Septuagint for WP8 and represents the most comprehensive critical edition of the Greek Old Testament. However, it remains incomplete, with the following books still in progress: *Canticum*, *Iosue*, *Iudices*, *Maccabaeorum IV*, *Paralipomenon liber I*, *Proverbia* and *Regnorum libri*. For these books, WP8 relies on the *editio altera* (R_LXX), a revision by Robert Hanhart of Alfred Rahlfs' 1935 *Handausgabe*, which is regarded by scholars as a "provisional" edition. WP8 is working with the texts of both the R_LXX and G_LXX in XML-OSIS format and also holds .txt files from the Göttingen volumes containing the critical apparatus and, where available, the Hexaplaric apparatus.

In sum, the editions used as source texts by the team are as follows:

- Septuagint (LXX) --- Critical editions:

1. G_LXX = R. Hanhart, J.W. Wevers, J. Ziegler *et al.* (eds), *Septuaginta: Vetus Testamentum Graecum auctoritate Academiae Scientiarum Gottingensis editum*, Göttingen: Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, 1931-.

Cf. <https://www.vandenhoeck-ruprecht-verlage.com/themen-entdecken/theologie-und-religion/systematische-theologie-religionsphilosophie/478/septuaginta-vetus-testamentum-graecum>

As mentioned earlier, digital volumes published so far (24 + *supplementum*) can be obtained through *Logos*, with the corresponding critical apparatus contained in separate files (for a fee: <https://www.logos.com/product/4951/gottingen-septuagint>).

2. R_LXX = A. Rahlfs, R. Hanhart (eds), *Septuaginta: Id est Vetus Testamentum graece iuxta LXX interpretes. Editio altera*, Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, 2006 (A. Rahlfs, ¹1935).

Cf. <https://www.academic-bible.com/en/bible/LXX/GEN.1> + <https://www.academic-bible.com/en/bible/LXXA/JDG.1> (alternative text)

WP8 obtained for research purposes the digitized edition of Rahlfs-Hanhart through *Logos* (for a fee: <https://www.logos.com/product/7080/septuagint>).

- Hexapla (H) --- Editions:

1. F_H = F. Field (ed.), *Origenis Hexaplorum quae supersunt; sive, Veterum Interpretum Graecorum in totum Vetus Testamentum fragmenta*, 2 vols., Hildesheim: Olms, 1964 (re-print; Oxford, ¹1875).

The two volumes of Field's edition are available in Archive.org, but the pdfs that can be downloaded from Archive are not of good quality:

<https://archive.org/details/origenishexaploro1origuoft/page/n5/mode/2up> +

<https://archive.org/details/origenishexaploro2origuoft/page/n1/mode/2up>

Members of the WP8 team are not currently using Field's edition because the information it contains converges with the second apparatus of the *Göttingen Septuagint* editions (see above: Hexaplaric apparatus). This second apparatus allows for comparison of the Septuagint's *lectiones* with the variant readings of other ancient Greek versions of the Hebrew Bible.

2. For a new critical edition of the extant Hexaplaric fragments, cf. <http://hexapla.org/>

The "Origen's Hexapla: A Critical Edition of the Extant Fragments" series includes for now only: J.D. Meade, *A Critical Edition of the Hexaplaric Fragments of Job 22-42*, Leuven: Peeters, 2020.

- Novum Testamentum (NT) --- Critical edition:

1. NA_NT = Eb. Nestle, Er. Nestle, B. Aland, K. Aland *et al.* (eds), *Novum Testamentum graece*, Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, ²⁸2012 (E. Nestle, ¹1898).

Cf. <https://www.academic-bible.com/en/bible/NA28/MAT.1>

WP8 obtained for research purposes the digitized edition of Nestle-Aland through *Logos* (for a fee: <https://www.logos.com/product/29980/nestle-aland-greek-new-testament-28th-edition-with-critical-apparatus>): the critical apparatus is also available there, although the variant readings are not linked to the text but available as a separate document.

Regarding the Latin Bible, the text of Jerome's Vulgate (VULG) – which, as is well known, became the standard reference biblical text for the Latin West already in Late Antiquity – is available in the digitized edition of R. Weber-R. Gryson on the website of the *Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft* (but without the apparatus, which is found in *Logos*). In contrast, access to the extant pre-Vulgate versions of the Old and the New Testaments, commonly known as *Vetus Latina* or *Veteres Latinae* (VL), is complicated by the fact that the only complete edition of these fragmentary versions was published in the 18th century by Pierre Sabatier, before the establishment of the textual critical method *sensu proprio*. Only a limited number of biblical books of the *Vetus Latina* have been critically edited in modern times for a Herder series, which does not have a digital edition:

- Vulgate (VULG) --- Critical edition:

1. W_VULG = R. Weber, R. Gryson (eds), *Biblia Sacra iuxta Vulgatam Versionem*, Stuttgart: Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, ⁵2007 (R. Weber, ¹1969).

Cf. <https://www.academic-bible.com/en/bible/VUL/GEN.1> + <https://www.academic-bible.com/en/bible/VULA/PSA.1> (alternative text)

WP8 obtained for research purposes the digitized edition of Weber-Gryson through *Logos* (for a fee: <https://www.logos.com/product/17846/biblia-sacra-vulgata-bsv-with-apparatus>): the apparatus is also available there, although the variant readings are not linked to the text but available as a separate document.

- *Veteres Latinae (VL)* --- Editions:

1. B_VL = *Vetus Latina: Die Reste der altlateinischen Bibel nach Petrus Sabatier neu gesammelt und herausgegeben von der Erzabtei Beuron*, Freiburg i.B.: Herder, 1949-

This critical edition (27 vols. in total) is not yet complete. For the volumes published so far cf. <https://www.herder.de/theologie-pastoral/shop/k2/reihen/vetus-latina/> + <https://www.herder.de/vetus-latina/>

WP8 has currently achieved with OCR (= Optical Character Recognition) technology the first digitized volume of Beuron's edition (containing Genesis in the *Vetus Latina*) for research aims, with the assistance of TREVENTUS Mechatronics GmbH (<https://www.treventus.com/about/company>).

2. S_VL = P. Sabatier (ed.), *Bibliorum Sacrorum latinae versiones antiquae seu Vetus Italica*, 3 vols., Reims: Reginaldus Florentain, 1743-1751.

The three volumes of Sabatier's edition are available in Archive.org, but the pdfs that can be downloaded from Archive are not of good quality:

<https://archive.org/details/bibliorumsacroruo1saba/page/n7/mode/2up> +
<https://archive.org/details/bibliorumsacroruo2saba/page/n7/mode/2up> +
<https://archive.org/details/Sabatier3>

WP8 obtained for research purposes the first two digitized volumes of Sabatier's edition through *Accordance* (for a fee: <https://www.accordancebible.com/product/vetus-latina-ot/>). These digitized documents were reviewed and cleaned of inaccuracies by the WP8 team. The third volume (containing the New Testament in the *Vetus Latina*) was digitized by some WP8 team members with OCR via *Transkribus* (<https://www.transkribus.org/>) from the printed edition.

On the Arabic-language side, the work of WP8 focused on conducting an inventory of all digital libraries and websites in Arabic that contain digitized texts relevant to the project, specifically the Quran, traditional literature (mainly collections of *ḥādīṭ* and the *Sīra al-Nabawiyyah*, i.e., the biographical genre of the Prophet), and *tafāsīr*. The primary reference sites identified include online libraries that offer a wide range of resources related to Islam in a broad sense. These include Quranic exegesis, *ḥādīṭ* compilations and other traditional texts, jurisprudence texts, Islamic theology, as well

as works relevant to other Quranic sciences, Arabic literature, and historical works, organized into categories. Examples containing large collections of Islamic texts include:

IslamWeb General Knowledge (<https://gk.islamweb.net>).

Al-Maktaba al-Shamila (<https://shamela.ws>).

Additionally, there are two resources that contain digitized texts of more specific literary genres:

Al-Tafsīr (<https://www.altafsir.com/index.asp>): maintained by the Royal Aal al-Bayt Institute for Islamic Thought in Jordan, this site provides access to over 150 Arabic Islamic texts. It includes Quranic exegesis (*tafsīr*) spanning all major schools of Islamic jurisprudence as well as theological, philosophical, and mystical perspectives.

Sunnah (<https://sunnah.com>): a comprehensive online platform dedicated to *ḥadīth* literature. It features an extensive, searchable collection of *ḥadīth*, organized by theme and sourced from well-known compilations such as Ṣaḥīḥ al-Buḥārī, Ṣaḥīḥ Muslim, Sunan `Abū Dāwūd, Sunan al-Tirmidī, Sunan al-Nasa`ī, Sunan Ibn Māğah, Muwaṭṭa` Malik, and Ṣamā`il al-Muḥammadiyyah, among others. The site provides detailed information on the chains of narration (*isnād*) and the narrators (*rāwī*), as well as translations and explanatory notes.

At present, these digital libraries are the primary source of texts in the OpenITI corpus and contribute significantly to its content. The **Open Islamicate Texts Initiative (OpenITI)** is a digital corpus of Islamicate texts founded in 2016 by Maxim Romanov, Sarah Bowen Savant, and Matt Miller (who each had been working on individual corpus projects). OpenITI aims to digitize and provide open access to a wide range of texts from the Islamicate tradition, covering literature, philosophy, theology, science, history, and more. The ultimate goal is to provide the textual infrastructure for new forms of macro-textual analysis and digital scholarship. Currently, OpenITI is not a digital library with a user interface, reading environment, or search functions, but it serves as the foundational groundwork and repository for future developments in the field. The preparation, selection, and collection of the material for WP8 are based on the texts collected by OpenITI from the various online sources mentioned above.

5.2 Target Texts

Given the extremely large size of the corpus of Greek and Latin patristic commentaries, a limited number of representative texts were initially chosen as case studies for a detailed analysis of biblical quotations and allusions, with the purpose of providing the IT team with a solid basis for machine learning and the elaboration of algorithms. On the Greek front, three works by Clement of Alexandria (c. 150 – 215 CE), namely the *Protrepticus*, the *Paedagogus* (Books 1 e 2), and the *Stromata* (Book 6), were selected for a first phase. On the Latin side, the research team focused on the twelve-book commentary *De Genesi ad litteram* by Augustine of Hippo (354 – 430 CE). As is customary in

philological research, the most accurate and recent critical editions of these exegetical works were used:

Clement of Alexandria --- Critical editions:

C. Mondésert, Clément d'Alexandrie. *Le protreptique (Sources Chrétiennes 2)*, Paris: Éditions du Cerf, ²1949 (¹1943).

M. Harl, H.-I. Marrou, C. Matray, C. Mondésert, Clément d'Alexandrie. *Le pédagogue*, 3 vols., vol. I, II (*Sources Chrétiennes* 70, 108), Paris: Éditions du Cerf, I:1960; II:1965.

P. Descourtieux, Clément d'Alexandrie. *Les Stromates*, vol. VI (*Sources Chrétiennes* 446), Paris: Éditions du Cerf, 1999.

Augustine of Hippo --- Critical edition:

J. Zycha, *Sancti Aureli Augustini De Genesi ad litteram libri duodecim: eiusdem libri capitula. De Genesi ad litteram imperfectus liber. Locutionum in Heptateuchum libri septem*, Pragae & Vindobonae & Lipsiae: Tempsky & Freyta, 1894.

The digital versions of Clement's works were prepared manually for research aims with the aid of the TLG database (<https://stephanus.tlg.uci.edu>), while the digital text of Augustine's *De Genesi ad litteram* was downloaded from the *Corpus Corporum* database created by the University of Zurich (<https://mlat.uzh.ch/>). The files were revised by the WP8 team members and uploaded on the platform INCEpTION to start the tagging process, which is aimed at manually highlighting references to the biblical texts that are certified as such by the team and thus may constitute a solid base for the machine learning process. INCEpTION is a platform developed between 2017 and 2022 by the Technische Universität Darmstadt and set for WP8 by the Institute of Science and Technologies of Information (ISTI) of the CNR in Pisa. It enabled the research team to prepare a training set for the models that ITSERR's engineers are currently completing based on the data received. It also allowed the team to design a workflow that does not deviate from the intertwining of high-level humanistic research and state-of-the-art Computer Science research. In fact, an environment such as INCEpTION

effectively integrates semantic annotation tools with machine learning processes (*active learning*), providing a simple web interface that is suitable for both our textual sources and the *modus operandi* of computer engineers.

Furthermore, in order to provide a computational account of the intertextual relationships connecting biblical texts and patristic literature, we have developed a classification that has the following features:²

1. It is *token-based*, because it is designed to interact with textual reuse search systems based on what the state of the art offers (*lemma-based*, *n-gram-based*, etc.). The tagging process originates and is performed on the target texts, which means that the token measure applies to them. The source texts used for confrontation, on the other hand, are atomized by a different measure, namely the biblical verse. This tagging process aims to distinguish the human approach to text, which is marked by precise procedures, from the machine approach, which is facilitated by short sequences of characters, but at the same time considers the needs of the IT team.
2. Our classification supports the interaction between the traditional categories of textual criticism and the techniques and modalities of computation. Indeed, on the one hand, our taxonomy considers a first type of intertextual reference, in which the words of the ancient Christian commentary/patristic work coincide totally or partially with some words of the biblical passage identified as source in one of the biblical versions available in the same language (with the associated apparatus variant readings). These references are assessed for their similarity to the source texts by a numerical proportion based on the number of identical tokens (see below, 6.). This type of references can be handled by “classical” algorithmics and “classical” artificial intelligence. A second type concerns intertextual references that do not share any identical token with their identified textual sources. These references, based on analogies of topic and context, are expected to be assessed by (and to be used as training materials for) Large Language Models.

Before explaining the sources and method of our work in more detail, a final reflection is needed on the strictly humanistic aims of the classification that is proposed here, a reflection that directly concerns the question at the heart of our research. As mentioned above, the research project of WP8 has three main objectives:

The first goal is to investigate the sacred texts that circulated in the ancient worlds, also with the purpose of shedding light on some lesser-known areas of biblical textual tradition – which may lead to the reappearance of currently “submerged” *Vorlagen* (or, more simply, of chains of identical scriptural reuses among ancient Christian authors that influence each other).

² This classification, its aims, and the methodology underlying it were first described in D. DAINESE, and A. MAMBELLI, *Intertestualità tra Bibbie e antichi commentari cristiani: l'esempio di simul nel De Genesi ad litteram di Agostino*, in “Lexicon Philosophicum: International Journal for the History of Texts and Ideas”, 11 (2023–2024), pp. 39-65. Open Access: <https://lexicon.cnr.it/ojs/index.php/LP/article/view/872/726>

The second aim is to study the heritages of Scriptures in different places and historical periods through the (broadly understood) Christian commentaries on the Bible(s), composed in both Greek and Latin from the patristic age to the late Byzantine period. This second line of research, pivoting around the history of reception, aims to rearrange and reconstruct the constitutive materials (and often the more or less conscious “mental” libraries) of the ancient authors of the commentaries, in order to restore at least part of the complex literary mosaic of biblical reworkings that is ancient Christian literature. In addition, beyond the purely quantitative and literary data, a reconstruction of the collective traditions and memories of religious communities in specific cultural settings and historical periods will be obtained by linking different authors of these exegetical works through their (in)visible “places of memory”, i.e. through the shared intertextual references that make sacred texts *ubiquitous*. In the opposite direction, this undertaking could also reveal if there are – and what are – biblical verses or passages that have been deprived of their heritage, that have not been taken up and transformed by the Fathers of the Church, that have fallen into the oblivion of time.

The third objective focuses on the study of intertextual references within the corpus of Arabic-language texts, consisting of the Quran, collections of *ḥādīṭ*, *sīra*, and *tafāsīr*. Specifically, this line of research aims at analyzing the modes of integration and reinterpretation of the Prophet’s Sayings in Quranic commentaries, considering both textual aspects — such as the degree of fidelity or variation compared to the formulations in canonical and non-canonical collections — and functional aspects, i.e., the purposes and exegetical practices for which these citations are employed. Through a methodological approach that combines quantitative and qualitative analysis with digital tools to identify both literal and non-literal references, this study seeks to shed light on the reciprocal relationships between *tafāsīr* and the literary genre dedicated to the Sayings of the Prophet, exploring the extent of references and the dynamics of textual reinterpretation. This research will contribute to reconstructing not only the networks of connection between these literary traditions but also the processes of transmission, transformation, and selection of the prophetic word, clarifying its role in shaping the religious and intellectual heritage of classical Islam.

Since intertextuality involves the (re)living of a biblical or prophetic text or tradition in a new and different context, this literary-historical phenomenon also has implications from an exegetical and theological point of view. The older biblical or prophetic text, once subjected to interpretation and more or less consciously deemed to be functional and suitable for transplantation into a new context, is transformed into something other than what it originally was. It, in turn, transforms the new text (whether it is also a biblical passage, a Christian or Islamic commentary, or something else) that received it to respond to new and specific needs, in view of a different audience. It follows, for example, that in order to study the phenomenon of biblical intertextuality, it is not sufficient – and may even be detrimental to understanding at a deeper level – to rigidly apply the classifications that have emerged in the history of scholarship (sometimes contradicting each other) in an attempt to capture the essence of a quotation, an echo or an allusion, mostly relying on a criterion of intentionality vs. non-intentionality. Rather, it is wiser to begin the analysis with a full awareness of the ancient exegetical methods used in the Jewish, Graeco-Roman or Islamic *milieux*, which explain

how a biblical verse (or part of it or a set of passages), a Quranic verse or a *ḥādīṭ* is traced and/or transformed in the target text.

Therefore, every intertextual relationship is also a relationship between meanings and is integrated into a continuous and inevitable dialectic between past and present, tradition and innovation, which characterizes all proto-Christian and Islamic literature (and all literature in general). Given this close and direct correlation between exegesis and intertextuality, when we refer to the latter phenomenon, we imply that an interpretive process of the biblical or Quranic text was also enacted by the author using it. The research path that a scholar must follow is obviously retrospective, since one can only start from the lexical, stylistic, and content-related traces that make the mode of reuse of one text in another more or less visible, and then go back to the exegesis that might have motivated that intertextual reference in that specific mode and precise context.³ The classification we propose responds to the first phase of this journey, that of searching for a method that keeps us as far away as possible from definitions given *a priori*, and to which only the intelligence and sensitivity of those who study the biblical, patristic and Islamic sources in depth will add proposals on the underlying reasons.

To illustrate even more clearly the work carried out by the WP8 research team on the above-mentioned *corpora* (and the classificatory categories applied to them), it may suffice to discuss the most relevant issues we have addressed in our analysis of Augustine's *De Genesis ad litteram* and its relationship to the Latin biblical tradition. What we will offer here is not, obviously, a systematic account of the strategies of biblical intertextuality at work in the Augustinian corpus – not even in *De Genesi ad litteram*.⁴ Rather, we will provide a comprehensive overview of our main criteria for preparing textual annotations in order to highlight the “granularity”, i.e. the textual complexity and exegetical stratification, of all our *corpora*.

³ For these and other broader and more detailed reflections on intertextuality and the exegetical methods that determine how a sacred text is reused in a later work, see A. MAMBELLI, «Verranno giorni...» nel Vangelo di Luca: l'influenza di Geremia LXX sulle profezie di Gesù riguardanti la distruzione di Gerusalemme, in A. MAMBELLI (ed.) "And from the daughter of Zion all her beauty is departed" (Lam 1:6). Reactions, Responses, and Reflections on the Fall of Jerusalem from the 1st to the 4th Century CE, monographic section of "Annali di Storia dell'Esegesi", 41, 2 (2024), pp. 275-310. This article, while focusing on a specific case study of intertextuality, draws from the extensive work carried out in WP8.

⁴ Specific case studies of the interaction between biblical intertextuality, philosophical influences, and cultural models in Augustine's *De Genesi ad litteram* and *De Civitate Dei* have been carried out by F. TUTRONE, *Aëriae Animae: Souls and Elements from the Roman Cosmos to the Christian Afterworld*, in M. Cesario, H. Magennis, and E. Ramazzina (eds.), *An Interdisciplinary Study of the Elements*, Vol. 3: *Air*, Leiden: Brill, 2025, forthcoming; F. TUTRONE, *Dreams, Texts, and Truths: Augustine on Hermeneutics and Oneirocriticism*, in P. Montanari (ed.), *Approaching Meaning: Background, Difference, Mind and the Hermeneutics of Ancient Texts. Essays in Memory of David Konstan*, Berlin-Boston: De Gruyter, 2025, forthcoming. Tutrone's two articles apply the insights of WP8 to the study of Augustine's discourse on psychology and oneirology, respectively.

6. Analysis

The analysis of textual *corpora* – in particular of the biblical versions and of some selected commentaries – has basically gone through three stages:

1. Identification of reference editions of biblical and patristic sources, as detailed above in 5.1 and 5.2. They constitute a privileged and necessary starting point for our work, which does not set out to critically discuss the work done by editors nor to make proposals for new critical editions. Within INCEpTION platform, only the text of the ancient commentary is annotated, adding references to all the biblical versions available in the same language as the commentary. The selected biblical sources, in their reference editions, currently serve as tools for manual annotation. As for the references to the individual volumes of the so-called *Vetus Latina* published by Beuron-Herder (B_VL), a further detail is always added to indicate the specific branch of the textual tradition mentioned by the editors in their main text (e.g., B_VL_C/E/L etc.; differently, in references such as B_VL_H and B_VL_V, the letters H and V are abbreviations for the Vulgate of Jerome [Hieronymus], whose text in Beuron-Herder's editions does not consistently correspond to that printed in the edition of Weber-Gryson mentioned above). As far as the Gospel of John is concerned, Beuron-Herder's *Vetus Latina* edition is not complete, just as it is not complete for many other biblical books. However, the manuscripts of John have at least been surveyed and transcribed in the *Vetus Latina Iohannes Synopsis 2.032* (<https://itseeweb.cal.bham.ac.uk/iohannes/vetuslatina/edition/index.html>; see also <https://edata.bham.ac.uk/61/>) according to a numbering that we currently include after B_VL (so, for references to the Gospel of John we will have, for example, B_VL_2/3/4/7/13/48 etc.; for the indirect tradition of John, see <https://itseewce.birmingham.ac.uk/citations/citation?language=lat>).
2. Selection of text strings to be annotated as intertextual references within the commentary. The selection is made on the basis of both the critical judgment of the annotator (in agreement with the entire research team) and the references to the Bibles already reported in scholarly literature, particularly in the notes of critical editions, in the notes or margins of translations into modern languages, in exegetical studies published in the last decades, and in the valuable online index of about 400,000 biblical references (provided as quotations or allusions) known as *BiblIndex*, which was developed by *Chrétiennes – HiSoMA* (<https://www.biblindex.org/en>).
3. Realization in INCEpTION of overlapping annotations, which highlight the degree of similarity between the annotated commentary string and a specific verse (or verses) of the selected Bible versions in their reference editions. The annotation process is based on the tagset developed and implemented in cooperation with the team of *Resilient Septuagint*.

The functions we envisaged for the annotation work, based on the needs of our specific research domain, were then set up in the INCEpTION platform and made visible, with a very intuitive graphical interface, in the work mask in the right column.

Fig. 1. Example from the INCEpTION dashboard.

These functions, with their pre-determined or free fields to be completed, are as follows:

<p>1. <i>Introductory Marker</i></p>	<p>With this function we highlight the formula that sometimes introduces the scriptural reference, making it explicit to the readers (sometimes the introductory formula is absent): e.g. <i>sicut legimus, scriptum est, dictum est, dicente Deo, scriptura dicens</i>.</p>
<p>2. <i>Reference Start or Reference Continuation</i></p>	<p>When a biblical reference is identified, it is highlighted from its first to last word using the <i>Reference Start</i> function. If an introductory marker or other elements interfere with an intertextual reference by segmenting it into several separate text strings, we use: a) the <i>Reference Start</i> function to report the entire portion of text that constitutes the beginning part of the biblical reference. b) the <i>Reference Continuation</i> function to</p>

	<p>indicate where the biblical reference continues, after the interruption, and where it ends. In this case, we repeat the tag twice, with identical data. When the tags are extracted, the portions that have been annotated as <i>Reference Start</i> and as <i>Reference Continuation</i>, respectively, are merged to form a single reference.</p>
<p>3. <i>Intertextual Reference</i></p>	<p>In this field the reference edition of a biblical version is selected, using pre-set abbreviations: for Latin versions, for example, W_VULG, then S_VL, then B_VL_C/E/L/H/V or, for the Gospel of John, B_VL_2/3/4/7/13/48 etc. (for these abbreviations, cf. above, 5.1).</p>
<p>3.a. <i>Book</i></p>	<p>For each edition of each biblical version placed in <i>Intertextual Reference</i>, the <i>Book</i> field indicates the title of the biblical book cited or alluded to in the ancient commentary. The titles of the biblical books are abbreviated in accordance with the <i>Handbook of Style</i> of the <i>Society of Biblical Literature</i> and are pre-set on the INCEPTION platform.</p>
<p>3.b. <i>Chapter</i></p>	<p>For each edition of each Bible version inserted in <i>Intertextual Reference</i>, we complete the <i>Chapter</i> field with the number of the biblical chapter that is in relation to the ancient commentary in the specific reference under consideration.</p>
<p>3.c. <i>Verse</i></p>	<p>For each edition of each Bible version placed in <i>Intertextual Reference</i>, the number of the biblical verse(s) that is in relation to the ancient commentary in that specific reference is entered.</p> <p>For some biblical books, the numbering of chapters and verses does not coincide in all versions (especially complex cases are, for example, those of the Psalms or the book of Daniel). Indeed, the differences found between the Hebrew Bible and the ancient Greek version of the Septuagint are inevitably reflected on the so-called <i>Vetus Latina</i>, a set of the earliest Latin translations of biblical texts from Greek, and on the Vulgate, for which Jerome claims to translate from the <i>hebraica veritas</i>. In these cases of</p>

	double numbering, the numbering of the edition of the biblical source under consideration is reported.
4. <i>Percentage of Similarity</i>	Once all the information about the biblical reference has been entered, the percentage of similarity between the annotated commentary string and the biblical passage quoted or alluded to is calculated.

Tab. 1. Functions for annotation work.

For this last operation, that is, the identification of the “weight” of an intertextual reference, we have chosen to adopt a purely numerical criterion, as independent as possible from preconceptions about the definitions of quotation, allusion, echo, intentional or unintentional cross-reference, but also from the recognition of synonymy and other semantic relationships. The percentage of similarity between a commentary string and a biblical passage (in its various versions) is thus obtained through the following steps:

<p>4.a. <i>Percentage of Similarity: Text-Text.</i></p>	<p>First, the number of terms (<i>token-based</i> criterion) that are repeated identically in the commentary and in the biblical text is counted against the total number of words that make up the commentary string identified as an intertextual reference (the basis for calculating the percentage of similarity is thus the annotated commentary). Each word involved in each intertextual relation that, being in the text of the commentary edition, also coincides morphologically with a term found in the biblical source edition is given the maximum weight of 1.</p> <p>Example 1: Aug., <i>Gen. ad litt.</i>, I 1 (edited by Zycha): <i>In principio fecit deus caelum et terram.</i> S_VL: <i>In principio fecit Deus caelum et terram</i> (Gen 1:1).</p> <p>7 out of 7 words are identical, so the <i>Percentage of Similarity</i> in the <i>Text-Text</i> field is filled with 100%. Where 100% is reached with the <i>Text-Text</i> comparison, the critical apparatus need not be analyzed and the same percentage should also be repeated in the <i>Percentage of Similarity: Final Run</i> field (see below).</p> <p>Example 2: Aug., <i>Gen. ad litt.</i>, I 13: <i>Terra autem erat inuisibilis et inconposita, et tenebrae erant super abyssum; et spiritus dei superferebatur super aquam.</i> W_VULG: <i>Terra autem erat inanis et vacua et tenebrae super faciem abyssi et spiritus Dei ferebatur super aquas</i> (Gen 1:2).</p> <p>11 out of 17 words are identical, 64.7% should therefore be entered in the <i>Percentage of Similarity: Text-Text</i> field. Since</p>
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<p>4.b. <i>Percentage of Similarity: Text-Apparatus.</i></p>	<p>To this first proportion made on the basis of the texts reconstructed by the editors, we must add the value of the possible presence of variants in the apparatus of the editions of both the commentary and the Bible(s). We assign to each variant a weight equal to half that of the word-to-text, thus a value of 0.5, since, as mentioned above, we rely on the work of the editors without critically questioning it.</p> <p>In the case in which there is a variant in the commentary apparatus or in the Bible apparatus that is identical to a word in the other text under consideration (or an omission that is also reflected in the other text), the value of that variant is added to the <i>Percentage of Similarity: Text-Apparatus</i> field.</p> <p>We take up the example used above:</p> <p>Example 2: Aug., <i>Gen. ad litt.</i>, l 13: <i>Terra autem erat inuisibilis et inconposita, et tenebrae erant super abyssum; et spiritus dei superferebatur super aquam.</i> In Zycha's apparatus we find <i>aquas</i> which in W_VULG is in the main text. W_VULG: <i>Terra autem erat inanis et vacua et tenebrae super faciem abyssi et spiritus Dei ferebatur super aquas</i> (Gen 1:2). In the apparatus of Weber-Gryson we find + <i>erant</i> which in Zycha is printed in the text. So, in this case <i>aquas</i> and <i>erant</i> are worth 2.9% (0.5:17 words = X:100), the sum of which is 5.8%. We enter this information in the field <i>Percentage of Similarity: Text-Apparatus</i>.</p>
<p>4.c. <i>Percentage of Similarity: Apparatus-Apparatus.</i></p>	<p>Having reached this point, the similarity between only apparatus is checked, which has a weight further halved: if there is no exact agreement between the commentary and the biblical passage in the intertextual reference, but an identical variant is found in the apparatus of their editions, it will have a value equal to 1/4 (0.25) of the value attributed to the single word in the text.</p> <p>Continuing with example 2 (see above), let us imagine for a moment (but this is not the case) that in Zycha's apparatus there is <i>informis</i> referred to the earth, and that this same variant is also found in the apparatus of Weber-Gryson, as resulting from some manuscripts.</p> <p>This would show that, in a different (more or less significant) strand of the tradition, the two texts might have been closer than they appear from the form given to them by the editors. This variant reading would be worth 0.25, so in our case 1.5% (0.25:17 words = X:100) should be entered in the field <i>Percentage of Similarity: Apparatus-Apparatus</i>.</p>
<p>4.d. <i>Percentage of Similarity: Final Run.</i></p>	<p>Finally, the variant values entered in the <i>Text-Apparatus</i> and <i>Apparatus-Apparatus</i> fields are summed with the value of the <i>Text-Text</i> field, to account for the possibility that the intertextual reference in the commentary traces the biblical passage in a (more) precise and literal way, but on the basis of a different strand of tradition than that printed in the text of the editions. The total should be entered in the field <i>Percentage of Similarity: Final</i></p>

	<p><i>Run.</i></p> <p>Resuming example n. 2 one last time, we will add up 64.7% of the text-text similarity and 5.8% of the text-apparatus concordance, resulting in a total similarity of 70.5% between Aug., <i>Gen. ad litt.</i>, l 13 (ed. Zycha), and W_VULG Gen 1,2, to be returned in the field <i>Percentage of Similarity: Final Run</i>.</p> <p>If the <i>informis</i> variant had actually been present in the apparatus and not just imagined as an example to fill the <i>Apparatus-Apparatus</i> field, the total percentage would have risen to 72%.</p>
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Tab. 2. Percentages of similarity between strings of the commentary and biblical passages.

Clearly, we repeat the same operation with respect to all biblical versions in their reference editions, including all the different letters of the Latin alphabet or the numbers of the manuscripts (in the case of the Gospel of John) of Beuron-Herder's *Vetus Latina*. As for the specific case of Sabatier's *Versio antiqua*, on the other hand, we point out that we do not take into account the content of the notes that follow the edited text, since they are far from being susceptible to being considered a critical apparatus. We therefore stop with S_VL at the *Text-Text* intersection (since we are aware that we may be faced with a case of circularity, as Sabatier reconstructed the *Vetus Latina* mainly on the basis of quotations from Augustine) and the percentage that emerges is reported identically in the *Final Run* field (skipping steps 4.b. and 4.c.).

This classification of intertextual relationships, which is characterized by a shared morphological and lexical basis, results from a purely scholarly need, namely, the need to restore the "granularity" of ancient texts, in particular the richness inherent in the textual plurality of Scriptures, which is itself both the reflection and the cause of a fruitful exegetical pluralism. This is the purpose of the inclusion of multiple biblical versions in the same language, with their multiple editions and apparatus variants. For this purpose, we make use of an immediate and transparent visual representation made up of overlapping annotations.

We are thus moving in a direction which is stubbornly contrary to most of the tools available to date for the study of Graeco-Roman antiquity, which (for admittedly understandable reasons) usually provide the text of only one edition for each work without critical apparatus (in the case of Latin biblical texts, they contain only the Vulgate of Weber-Gryson), thus giving the erroneous impression that the Bible circulating in the ancient Graeco-Roman world was one for each language, monolithic and unchanging. While there is unanimous consensus among scholars that such a simplification does not correspond to reality, we also know that the technologies we use on a daily basis affect the quality of our research and are capable of accelerating or curbing the possibility of generating significant theoretical advances in our fields of investigation.

The classification proposed here also considers those intertextual relationships that are based on the recurrence of one or more terms (though without exact morphological coincidence), or on equivalence in syntactic structure, or on exclusively thematic similarities that usually involve several biblical verses. In these cases, after following the above-mentioned process up to *Chapter*, the researcher enters in the *Verse* field the verse or the first of a set of Bible verses that turn out to be the closest to the annotated commentary passage in terms of lexicon and/or syntax and/or subject matter. Then, the annotator must fill in all four subsequent fields of *Percentage of Similarity* (*Text-Text*; *Text-Apparatus*; *Apparatus-Apparatus*; *Final Run*) with 0%. Going beyond the numeric value, which here does not quantify the degree of similarity (the only possible alternative would have been to arbitrarily assign a low percentage), we leave in this way a trace of the annotation, and thus a piece of information is ultimately extracted that is certainly no less important, from the historical, literary, and exegetical-theological point of view.

Example 1. Aug., *Gen. ad litt.*, l 3 (Zycha): *per uerbum suum fecit, quidquid fecit.*

The Augustinian passage refers not only to the Word (*Verbum*) of the Gospel of John 1:3, through which all that exists was made, but also to the first chapter of Genesis (Gen), in which the God of Israel creates all things through His Word. For Gen 1, we insert verse 3 in the *Verse* field, because it is clear from what Augustine writes just before about the origin of light that the commentary refers to this verse – and not by accident, since it is the first verse that mentions the powerful creative capacity of the Word of God: *dixitque* [or *et dixit* depending on the biblical version] *Deus: fiat lux et facta est lux.* Beginning with Gen 1:3, *dixit Deus* is repeated several times within the same biblical chapter: thus, for Augustine it represents the first step in the development of his exegetical thought on creation (*Percentage of Similarity: 0%*).

The following example, which is only slightly different, could be called “mixed” within our classification:

Example 2. Aug., *Gen. ad litt.*, l 2 (Zycha): *linguarum diuersitas, quae postea facta est in aedificatione turris post diluuium.*

Augustine’s passage clearly refers to the tower of Babel in Genesis, chapter 11. It consists of the following elements: a short final coda that presents an exact coincidence with a biblical verse from the tale to which it refers (*post diluuium* is found identically in Gen 11:10 in all biblical versions); an initial portion of the textual string (*linguarum diuersitas, quae postea facta est in aedificatione turris*), that instead lacks a common textual basis (understood again as both lexical and morphological coincidence), but nevertheless refers quite clearly to Gen 11:1-10.

In this case, *post diluuium* is annotated separately by entering verse 10 in the *Verse* field and 100% as the percentage of similarity (*Text-Text* and *Final Run*). The preceding portion of the textual string running from *linguarum* to *turris* has 0% similarity percentage in all its fields (*Text-Text*; *Text-Apparatus*; *Apparatus-Apparatus*; *Final Run*); in the *Verse* field, verse 4 of Gen 11 is entered this time, because it is the one that specifically mentions the tower for the first time (*turrem*, which only morphologically does not coincide with Augustine’s *turris*). In this way the information regarding the exact coincidence of *post diluuium* is not lost, nor is lost the reference to the larger passage in Gen 11:1-10.

An intertextual reference that shows only thematic similarities with its source, and whose wording in the early Christian commentary does not coincide (even leaving aside morphological coincidence) with any word of the biblical passage identified in any of the biblical versions available in the same language (with the related apparatus variants), represents a more veiled reference, that appeals to the reader’s memory and culture and calls for a correct understanding. In this kind of intertextual relationships, the interpretive ground can become slippery, and sometimes it is hard to discern the boundary separating purely textual influence from cultural influence (or influence based on a shared theological perspective). Precisely for this reason, some scholars combine the direct literary

dependence of one text on another/others (*intertextual relations*) with the concepts of *common motifs and images* which, within a literary-historical context that was largely made up of orality and memory, influenced various proto-Christian works, since they were used in the same cultural *milieu*. It is true that in several cases the similarity between two texts may simply be the unconscious result of common traditions, imagery and motifs, but it is equally true that in the ancient world even these elements mostly emerge from the comparison of written sources that are known to us. Moreover, it is important to remember that, for patristic authors, the Bible is not just a text; it is itself a cultural-religious matrix and fabric. Therefore, the references remain somehow within a form of “textuality” (a text can also be remembered by heart) and especially within a dialogue (*inter*) with ancient biblical versions, which deserves to be investigated in all its complexity.

To address this complexity, as far as the annotations in Greek are concerned, the WP8 team, in collaboration with *Resilient Septuagint* team, has developed an expansion of the classification, which aims to handle textual similarities beyond the presence of identical tokens in the source and target texts. The methodological framework of the expanded semantic annotation rests on a concentric circles approach that progressively enlarges the numerical classification of intertextual references, going from the exact correspondence to a broader semantic frame. The goal is for the annotation to be able to include and classify other degrees of similarity, which allows the team to analyze and annotate more examples of textual reuse, which in turn may lead to include more and more textual material in the recall of the search engine.

The concentric circles that capture the semantic expansion of the classification are visible in the following image, which gives an overview of the added fields that are now present on the INCEpTION platform for the tagging of Greek intertextual references and that will be shown in detail below:

Fig. 2. Visualization of the expanded WP8's classification.

In order to expand on the representation of the distance between the two texts, we consider those other degrees of similarity, for each of which the calculation is repeated according to the same principle shown above. The tagging is performed on all levels on each string identified as an intertextual reference.

Fig. 3. Example of tag on Clement of Alexandria's *Paedagogus* (l.1.1) on INCEpTION.

The following steps are undertaken for each tag and are here shown by the example of a comparison between the target text by Clement of Alexandria (*Paedagogus*, l.1.1) and the source text NA_NT (New Testament in the most recent Nestle-Aland edition, see above 5.1) of 2 Timothy (2 Tim) 2:19. The comparison has been prompted by the indication in the notes of the above-mentioned edition of Clement's work (*Sources Chrétiennes* 70). The text goes as follows:

Συγκεκριρότητα κρηπίς ἀληθείας, ὡ παῖδες ὑμεῖς, ἡμῖν αὐτοῖς, ἀγίου νεῦ μεγάλου θεοῦ θεμέλιος γνῶσεως ἀρραγῆς, προτροπὴ καλὴ, δι' ὑπακοῆς εὐλόγου ζωῆς αἰδίου ὄρεξις, νοερωῶ καταβληθεῖσα χωρίω.

These lines, which mark the beginning of the *Paedagogus*, illustrate the metaphor of the divine architect, who prepares the structure of knowledge for His creatures. The metaphor is clearly drawn from a biblical image, which recurs in different passages of the New Testament. The tag is in this case repeated for each of them (namely, 1 Cor 3:10; Eph 2:20; 2 Tim 2:19). As an example of the classification, here only the third one is presented.

- 1. Token:** for the principles of classification used on this level. It should be noted that the case of *Apparatus-Apparatus* correspondence is extremely rare, since the works of Clement of Alexandria hardly present variant readings, but the tagging set still maintains this possibility, in case of exceptional instances. The result of this stage of tagging is inserted via the field *Percentage of Similarity Text* (repeated in the fields *Text-Text*, *Text-Apparatus*, *Apparatus-Apparatus*, *Final Run*). In the example, among the 26 words that constitute the highlighted intertextual reference, only two tokens appear identical in the two texts (θεμέλιος and θεοῦ), so the field *Percentage of Similarity Text: Text-Text* has been filled with 7.69% ($2:26 = X:100$). The apparatus does not add relevant information, so the same percentage is repeated in the *Final Run* of the field.
- 2. Lemma:** all the tokens that were not found identical in the first step (in this case the remaining 24) are considered for the *Lemma* selection. Each token that can be referred to the same lemma as one that is present in the edited text of each biblical verse identified as source is given the full value 1, whereas the correspondence at the lemma level between a text and an apparatus is given 0.5. The proportion is calculated according to the same principles used with the tokens. The result of this stage of tagging is inserted via the field *Percentage of Similarity Lemma* (repeated in the fields *Text-Text*, *Text-Apparatus*, *Apparatus-Apparatus*, *Final Run*). In our example, only one token in the target can refer to the same lemma as one word from the New Testament passage (the pronoun αὐτός, in the dative plural in Clement and genitive singular in the New Testament), so the field *Percentage of Similarity Lemma: Text-Text* is filled with 3.85% ($1:26 = X:100$). The same is repeated in the *Final Run*, since the apparatus does not add any further information.
- 3. Root:** all the tokens that have not been classified so far are considered for the *Root* selection (in our case 23 are remaining). Each token that can be referred to the same etymological root as one that is present in the selected source is here given its numeric value. The result of this stage of tagging is inserted via the field *Percentage of Similarity Root* (repeated in the fields *Text-Text*, *Text-Apparatus*, *Apparatus-Apparatus*, *Final Run*). In the example, one token falls under this category (the genitive singular γνώσεως in Clement and the aorist ἔγνων in the New Testament, which both derive from the same root indicating “knowledge”). The field is thus filled with 3.85% ($1:26 = X:100$). The same is repeated in the *Final Run*, since the apparatus does not add any further information.
- 4. Synonym:** all the tokens that have not been classified so far are considered for the *Synonym* selection (in the example 22 are remaining). In this case, the team establishes whether they can be considered synonymous with one (or more) tokens in the identified source text. The assessment is based on the team domain knowledge and linguistic expertise. There is a tool that classifies words in Ancient Greek by synonymy in the Ancient Greek WordNet, but it still contains noise that makes it unsuitable for the classification (which remains, in any case, a human research endeavour). The result of this stage of tagging is inserted via the field *Percentage of Similarity Synonyms* (repeated in the fields *Text-Text*, *Text-Apparatus*, *Apparatus-Apparatus*, *Final Run*). In the example, the words στερεός and ἀππαγή can be considered as synonyms, both indicating the idea of “firmness”. The field is thus

filled with 3.85% (1:26 = X:100). The same is repeated in the *Final Run*, since the apparatus does not add any further information.

5. **Structure:** this last level is the furthest possibility of classification of similarity developed by the team and is based on different principles, since it needs to address questions of intertextual dependence that are not necessarily token based. For all semantic items (be they tokens, syntagms, syntactical dispositions, metaphors, rhetorical figures or other) that have not found a place within the classification so far, the team discusses the pertinence of still signaling a similarity that goes beyond those identified by the means of textual semantics listed above. The team goes on to attribute a score (from 1 to 10) to the entire string to further address the pertinence of the intertextual reference. The score is inserted via the field *Similarity Score Structure* on the platform (repeated in the fields *Text-Text*, *Text-Apparatus*, *Apparatus-Apparatus*, *Final Run*).

The field *Note* can be used at all stages of the tagging process, but it is especially relevant for the last one, in which the team sometimes feels the need to take notes of the discussion that led to the attribution of a *Similarity Score Structure*.

Each step can be skipped (and the corresponding fields left blank) if the text does not contain any token that falls in the specific category. This means that annotations are included even if the only similarity is found at the *Structure* level. Instead of just signaling the reference as it was the case with Latin, it is now possible to give the similarity a score that testifies the agreement of the team on the value of the reference itself. One example of this possibility is found in *Paedagogus*, 1.5.22, where the words ἐγείλα δὲ κάκεινος τοῦ θανάτου ἠελυμένος are strongly reminiscent of the passage in Gen 22:13 in which Isaac is saved from his father's willingness to sacrifice him, yet no words can be found in the text that would fit in the semantic categories mentioned above. The team has given this text 2 as a *Similarity Score Structure*, to safeguard the information on the intertextual dependence even in the absence of a strictly token-based similarity.

The final tagging set on INCEPTION thus includes the following fields:

- *Percentage of Similarity Text: Text-Text*
- *Percentage of Similarity Text: Text-Apparatus*
- *Percentage of Similarity Text: Apparatus-Apparatus*
- *Percentage of Similarity Text: Final Run*
- *Percentage of Similarity Lemma: Text-Text*
- *Percentage of Similarity Lemma: Text-Apparatus*
- *Percentage of Similarity Lemma: Apparatus-Apparatus*
- *Percentage of Similarity Lemma: Final Run*

- *Percentage of Similarity Root: Text-Text*
- *Percentage of Similarity Root: Text-Apparatus*
- *Percentage of Similarity Root: Apparatus-Apparatus*
- *Percentage of Similarity Root: Final Run*
- *Percentage of Similarity Synonyms: Text-Text*
- *Percentage of Similarity Synonyms: Text-Apparatus*
- *Percentage of Similarity Synonyms: Apparatus-Apparatus*
- *Percentage of Similarity Synonyms: Final Run*
- *Similarity Score Structure: Text-Text*
- *Similarity Score Structure: Text-Apparatus*
- *Similarity Score Structure: Apparatus-Apparatus*
- *Similarity Score Structure: Final Run*
- *Note*

The meticulous classification obtained with this metric is largely an arbitrary representation, but it seems indicative of the composite nature of intertextual relations between the biblical texts and the ancient authors who made use of them. By assigning different percentages to different degrees of similarity, the picture of a text in relation to its sources appears more nuanced and inspires a scholarly debate on the nature, form, and context of the identified nuances. A classification that may appear rigid at a first glance thus becomes a valuable tool to address different phenomena in textual reuse, which allows scholars to deepen their understanding of the writing habits of an ancient author, going beyond the simple indication of a generic parallelism with the biblical text, which is often all that is found on this matter in the available editions (both with or without “cf.”).

For the analysis of Arabic-language texts, the annotation work was organized according to specific categories in line with the nature of the corpus. Also in this case, the process was performed using the INCEPTION platform, where overlapping annotations were used to highlight the degrees of similarity between the annotated section of a *tafsīr* and various reference texts, including the Quran, the Sayings of the Prophet, and other exegetical works. A particular challenge in annotating prophetic Sayings is the lack of precise references to the sources used by the exegetes in the editions of Islamic commentaries.

The methodological work for the study of the Arabic corpus was conducted in parallel with that developed and adopted for Latin. In this case, a precise tag-set was defined, following the general structure of the categories used for Latin and Greek, but adapted to the specifics of the Arabic corpus. The main categories include:

1. ***Introductory Marker***

It identifies expressions that introduce references to the Quran, the Sayings of the Prophet, or other commentaries, such as *qāla ta'ālā* (God said), *qāla rasūl Allāh* (the Messenger of God said), *qāla al-mufassirūn* (the exegetes said). In the case of a *ḥādīṭ*, specific subcategories were added to tag the transmission chains (*isnād*) preceding the *ḥādīṭ* and the direct speech itself (*matn*).

2. ***Reference Start or Reference Continuation***

It is a category shared with Latin and Greek to identify the beginning or continuation of a quotation or allusion.

3. ***Intertextual Reference***

This field allows to classify intertextual references, distinguishing between:

- a. Quran – *sūra* (chapter) and *āya* (verse) must be indicated.
- b. Sunna – It is necessary to specify whether it is a collection of *ḥādīṭ* or the *sīra*. In the case of a *ḥādīṭ*, the following metadata are annotated:

- Author of the collection (Author).
- Title of the collection (Source).
- Title of the book (Book) and chapter number (Chapter).

Since the numbering of *ḥādīṭ* is not consistent across printed editions, only the books and chapter numbers are annotated as stable elements.

In the case of the *sīra*, details of the work and edition are provided: author, title, volume, and page.

- c. *Tafsīr* – Details of the work and edition are provided: author, title of the work, volume, and page.

4. ***Percentage of Similarity***

The percentage of similarity between the annotated text and the source is calculated with the same numerical criteria used for Latin. For Arabic texts, the comparison is done only at the *Text-Text* level, excluding critical apparatus, which are often absent in printed editions.

7. Findings

7.1 Results from a Case Study in Latin: *simul*

The *Vetus Latina*, in the Beuron Archabbey edition published by Herder and edited for the book of Sirach (Sir) by Walter Thiele, does not attest for Sir 18.1 textual versions other than Weber-Gryson's Vulgate. However, its apparatus registers more manuscripts than Weber-Gryson's edition. Therefore, the percentages of similarity between Augustine's text and Thiele's Vulgate and between Augustine's text and Weber-Gryson's Vulgate may be different. We can first consider three simple cases, all of which are found in Aug., *Gen. ad litt.*, IV 33.

The passage in question is as follows:

de quo enim creatore scriptura ista narravit, quod sex diebus consummaverit opera sua, de illo alibi non utique dissonanter scriptum est, quod creaverit omnia simul. Ac per hoc et istos dies sex uel septem, uel potius unum sexies septiesue repetitum, simul fecit, qui fecit omnia simul. Quid ergo opus erat sex dies tam distincte dispositeque narrari? Quia scilicet hi, qui non possunt uidere, quod dictum est: creavit omnia simul, nisi cum eis sermo tardius incedat, ad id, quo eos ducit, peruenire non possunt.

Here the editor, Josef Zycha, indicates only two types of reference to Sir 18:1: one indirect (we would say, according to the classical designation, an allusion) marked by a "cf.", relating to the text *creaverit omnia simul*, and one direct (a quotation) for the text *creavit omnia simul*.

With our grading system, *creaverit omnia simul* is given a 66.67% for text-text similarity alone in Sabatier (S_VL), Thiele's Vulgate (B_VL), and Weber-Gryson's Vulgate (W_VULG) because two out of three words recur identically in all three versions, namely *omnia* and *simul*. As for *creavit omnia simul*, however, all three versions have a 100% similarity. In addition, however, we thought we could find a third reference, positioned between the other two, namely *simul fecit, qui fecit omnia simul*, and we related it to the Vulgate's *qui vivit in aeternum creavit omnia simul* (again for Sir 18:1). Notwithstanding a metric-rhythmic correspondence (*simul fecit | qui fecit omnia simul*, on the one hand, and *qui vivit in aeternum | creavit omnia simul*, on the other), the presence of the adverb *simul* in both the Augustinian passage and the Vulgate text as well as the presence of a variant (*fecit*) for *creavit* only in the manuscripts surveyed by Thiele, and not in those of Weber-Gryson's edition, allow us to recognize a certain percentage of similarity:

	W_VULG: <i>qui vivit in aeternum creavit omnia simul</i>	S_VL: <i>qui vivit in aeternum creavit omnia simul</i>	B_VL_V: <i>qui vivit in aeternum creavit [variant fecit] omnia simul</i>
Text-text similarity:	3 out of 6 words in the Augustinian string (<i>qui, omnia, simul</i>), therefore 50%	3 out of 6 words in the Augustinian string (<i>qui, omnia, simul</i>), therefore 50%	3 out of 6 words in the Augustinian string (<i>qui, omnia, simul</i>), therefore 50%
Apparatus similarity (apparatus-text/apparatus-apparatus):	0%	0%	1 word, between a variant of the biblical version and Augustine's text (<i>fecit</i>), thus of half weight, 8.33%
Total:	50%	50%	58.33%

Tab. 3. Similarities between Augustine's text and Sir 18:1.

A more complex case is Aug., *Gen. ad litt.*, IV 34:

quomodo ergo dicimus septies repetitam lucis illius praesentiam per angelicam cognitionem a uespere ad mane, cum ipsa tria simul, id est et diem et uesperam et mane semel ei habere suffecerit, cum simul universam creaturam, sicut simul facta est, et in primis atque incommutabilibus rationibus, per quas condita est, contempleretur propter diem et in eius ipsius natura cognosceret propter uesperam et creatorem ex ipsa etiam inferiore cognitione propter mane laudaret?

Here Augustine's references to Sir 18:1 are of greater interest, as they are inserted in the tradition of Gen 1 (1:5, 8, 13, 19, 23, 31), allowing us to follow the formation of Augustine's thought on the basis of his reuse, paraphrase, and exegesis of biblical texts. Zycha has not referred to any biblical passage. Clearly, he does not refer to Sir 18:1 for editorial reasons, as two references to the same passage had just been reported in a footnote. But the same is probably true also of the Gen 1 passages, since Genesis is the biblical book that Augustine is commenting on in this work. Since we have to prepare a dataset for a machine learning task, our outlook on this subject is very different. Therefore, we have considered all the passages in which the text of

Gen 1 refers to the recapitulation of divine activity from evening to morning. In the Augustinian text above, we were able to identify five intertextual references. The first concerns the pericope *septies repetitam lucis illius praesentiam per angelicam cognitionem a vespere ad mane*, which blends the references in Gen 1 to the transit from the first six evenings to the first six mornings (although Augustine reports the number seven, according to what some manuscripts attest).

The second reference, on the other hand, is a reference to Sir 18:1, which Augustine had previously echoed quite explicitly. Augustine also uses this reference immediately after *id est* to elucidate Gen 1:5, 8, 13, 19, 23, 31. In this string, which attests *ipsa tria simul*, only the token *simul* appears in both Augustine and the biblical text of the three available editions of the Vulgate (Thiele, Weber-Gryson, Sabatier). Thus, since neither Zycha’s edition nor the Bibles’ variants attest to anything of note, the overall percentage of similarity reaches 33.33% for each.

As mentioned above, the *id est* that immediately follows justifies the juxtaposition between the string *et diem et vesperam et mane semel ei habere suffecerit* and the reference to Sir 18:1 in the *ipsa tria simul* just referred to. We are at the third - and most interesting - intertextual reference of the five identified. In this case, in *et diem et vesperam et mane semel ei habere suffecerit*, we could be faced with a class of zero-percentage references (which perhaps should be entrusted to the “oracular” perception of *deep learning*). Still, the presence of the variant *semel* in place of *simul* in Thiele’s edition – a word that occurs in Augustine’s text – allows the percentage of similarity between Thiele’s Vulgate and Augustine’s text to rise to 5%. On the other hand, the percentage remains zero for the text in Weber-Gryson’s and Sabatier’s editions.

As for the references to Gen 1:5, 8, 13, 19, 23, 31, the results of our analysis can be summarized in the following tables:

	W_VULG: <i>appellavitque e lucem diem et tenebras noctem factumque est vespere et mane dies unus</i>	B_VL_L: <i>et vocavit deus lucem diem et tenebras vocavit noctem et facta est vespera et factum est mane dies unus</i>	B_VL_H: <i>appellavitque lucem diem et tenebras noctem factumque est vespere et mane dies unus</i>	S_VL: <i>et vocavit deus lucem diem et tenebras vocavit noctem et facta est vespera et factum est mane dies unus</i>
Text-text similarity:	4 out of 10 words (<i>diem, et, et, mane</i>),	5 out of 10 words (<i>diem, et, et, mane</i>), therefore 50%.	4 out of 10 words (<i>diem, et, et, mane</i>), so 40%	5 out of 10 words (<i>diem, et, et, mane</i>),

	so 40%			therefore 50%.
Apparatus similarity (apparatus-text/apparatus-apparatus):	0 words then 0%	1 word between the biblical version and a variant of Augustine's text (<i>vespera</i> instead of <i>vesperam</i>), thus of half the weight, 5%	0 words then 0%	1 word, between the biblical version and a variant of Augustine's text (<i>vespera</i> instead of <i>vesperam</i>), thus of half the weight, 5%
Total:	40 %	55%	40%	55%

Tab. 4. Similarities between Augustine's text and Gen 1:5.

	W_VULG: <i>vocavitque deus firmamentum caelum et factum est vespere et mane dies secundus</i>	B_VL_L: <i>et vocavit deus firmamentum caelum et vidit deus quia bonum est et facta est vespera et factum est mane dies secundus</i>	B_VL_H: <i>vocavitque deus firmamentum caelum et factum est vespere et mane dies secundus</i>	S_VL: <i>et vocavit deus firmamentum caelum et vidit deus quia bonum est et facta est vespera et factum est mane dies secundus</i>
Text-text similarity :	3 out of 10 words (<i>et, et, mane</i>), so 30%	4 words out of 10 (<i>et, et, et, mane</i>), so 40%	3 out of 10 words (<i>et, et, mane</i>), so 30%	4 words out of 10 (<i>et, et, et, mane</i>), so 40%
Apparatus similarity (apparatus-text/apparatus-apparatus):	0 words then 0%	1 word between the biblical version and a variant of Augustine's text (<i>vespera</i> instead of <i>vesperam</i>), thus of half the weight, 5%	0 words then 0%	1 word, between the biblical version and a variant of Augustine's text (<i>vespera</i> instead of <i>vesperam</i>), thus of half the weight,

				5%
Total:	30%	45%	30%	45%

Tab. 5. Similarities between Augustine’s text and Gen 1:8.

	W_VULG: <i>factumque est vespere et mane dies tertius</i>	B_VL_L: <i>et facta est vespera et factum est mane dies tertius</i>	B_VL_H: <i>factumque est vespere et mane dies tertius</i>	S_VL: <i>et facta est vespera et factum est mane dies tertius</i>
Text-text similarity :	2 out of 10 words (<i>et, mane</i>), so 20%	3 out of 10 words (<i>et, et, mane</i>), so 30%	2 out of 10 words (<i>et, mane</i>), therefore 20%.	3 out of 10 words (<i>et, et, mane</i>), so 30%
Apparatus similarity (apparatus- text/apparatus- apparatus):	1 word, between the variants of the biblical version (<i>et</i>) and Augustine’s text, hence of half the weight, 5%	1 word, between the biblical version and a variant of Augustine’s text (<i>vespera</i>), thus half- weighted, 5%	1 word, between the variants of the biblical version (<i>et</i>) and Augustine’s text, thus of halved weight, 5%	1 word, between the biblical version and a variant of Augustin’s text (<i>vespera</i>), so by half the weight, 5%
Total:	25%	35%	25%	35%

Tab. 6. Similarities between Augustine's text and Gen 1:13.

	W_VULG: <i>et factum est vespere et mane dies quartus</i>	B_VL_L: <i>et facta est vespera et factum est mane dies quartus</i>	B_VL_H: <i>et factum est vespere et mane dies quartus</i>	S_VL: <i>et facta est vespera et fac- tum est mane dies quartus</i>
Text-text similarity:	3 out of 10 words (<i>et, et, mane</i>), so 30%	3 out of 10 words (<i>et, et, mane</i>), so 30%	3 out of 10 words (<i>et, et, mane</i>), so 30%	3 out of 10 words (<i>et, et, mane</i>), so 30%
Apparatus similarity (apparatus - text/appar atus- apparatus)	0 words then 0%	1 word, between the biblical version and a variant of Augustine's text (<i>vespera</i>), thus half- weighted, 5%	0 words then 0%	1 word, between the biblical version and a variant of the Augustinian text (<i>vespera</i>), thus half- weighted, 5%
Total:	30%	35%	30%	35%

Tab. 7. Similarities between Augustine's text and Gen 1:19.

	W_VULG : <i>et factum est vespere et mane dies quintus</i>	B_VL_L: <i>et facta est vespera et factum est mane dies quintus</i>	B_VL_H: <i>et factum est vespere et mane dies quintus</i>	S_VL: <i>et facta est vespere et factum est mane dies quintus</i>
Text-text similarity :	3 out of 10 words (<i>et, et, mane</i>), so 30%	3 out of 10 words (<i>et, et, mane</i>), so 30%	3 out of 10 words (<i>et, et, mane</i>), so 30%	3 out of 10 words (<i>et, et, mane</i>), therefore 30%

Apparatus similarity (apparatus-text/apparatus-apparatus):	0 words, hence 0%	1 word, between the biblical version and a variant of Augustine's text (<i>vespera</i>), thus half-weighted, 5%	0 words then 0%	1 word, between the biblical version and a variant of Augustine's text (<i>vespera</i>), thus of half the weight, 5%
Total	30%	35%	30%	35%

Tab. 8. Similarities between Augustine's text and Gen 1:23.

	W_VULG: <i>viditque deus cuncta quae fecit et erant valde bona et factum est vespere et mane dies sextus</i>	B_VL_L: <i>et vidit deus omnia quaecumque fecit et ecce bona valde et facta est vespera et factum est mane dies sextus</i>	B_VL_H: <i>viditque deus cuncta quae fecit et erant valde bona et factum est vespere et mane dies sextus</i>	S_VL: <i>et vidit deus omnia quae fecit et ecce bona valde et facta est vespera et factum est mane dies sextus</i>
Text-text similarity:	4 words out of 10 (<i>et, et, et, mane</i>), so 40%	4 words out of 10 (<i>et, et, et, mane</i>), so 40%	4 words out of 10 (<i>et, et, et, mane</i>), so 40%	4 words out of 10 (<i>et, et, et, mane</i>), so 40%

Apparatus similarity (apparatus-text/apparatus-apparatus):	0 words therefore 0%	1 word, between the biblical version and a variant of Augustine's text (<i>vespera</i>), thus of half the weight, 5%	0 words then 0%	1 word, between the biblical version and a variant of the Augustinian text (<i>vespera</i>), thus half-weighted, 5%
Total	40%	45%	40%	45%

Tab. 9. Similarities between Augustine’s text and Gen 1:31.

INCEpTION’s interface allows for a very intuitive graphical representation of this complex picture:

Reference Start S_VL Gen 1 31 40.0 5.0 0.0 45.0
Reference Start B_VL_H Gen 1 31 40.0 0.0 0.0 40.0
Reference Start B_VL_L Gen 1 31 40.0 5.0 0.0 45.0
Reference Start W_VULG Gen 1 31 40.0 0.0 0.0 40.0
Reference Start S_VL Gen 1 23 30.0 5.0 0.0 35.0
Reference Start B_VL_H Gen 1 23 30.0 0.0 0.0 30.0
Reference Start B_VL_L Gen 1 23 30.0 5.0 0.0 35.0
Reference Start W_VULG Gen 1 23 30.0 0.0 0.0 30.0
Reference Start S_VL Gen 1 19 30.0 5.0 0.0 35.0
Reference Start B_VL_H Gen 1 19 30.0 0.0 0.0 30.0
Reference Start B_VL_L Gen 1 19 30.0 5.0 0.0 35.0
Reference Start W_VULG Gen 1 19 30.0 0.0 0.0 30.0
Reference Start S_VL Gen 1 13 30.0 5.0 0.0 35.0
Reference Start B_VL_H Gen 1 13 20.0 5.0 0.0 25.0
Reference Start B_VL_L Gen 1 13 30.0 5.0 0.0 35.0
Reference Start W_VULG Gen 1 13 20.0 5.0 0.0 25.0
Reference Start S_VL Gen 1 8 40.0 5.0 0.0 45.0
Reference Start B_VL_H Gen 1 8 30.0 0.0 0.0 30.0
Reference Start B_VL_L Gen 1 8 40.0 5.0 0.0 45.0
Reference Start W_VULG Gen 1 8 30.0 0.0 0.0 30.0
Reference Start S_VL Gen 1 5 50.0 5.0 0.0 55.0
Reference Start B_VL_H Gen 1 5 40.0 0.0 0.0 40.0
Reference Start B_VL_L Gen 1 5 50.0 5.0 0.0 55.0
Reference Start W_VULG Gen 1 5 40.0 0.0 0.0 40.0
Reference Start S_VL Sir 18 1 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0
Reference Start B_VL_V Sir 18 1 0.0 5.0 0.0 5.0
Reference Start W_VULG Sir 18 1 0.0 0.0 0.0 0.0

et diem et uesperam et mane semel ei habere suffecerit.

Fig. 4. Graphic representation in INCEpTION.

Finally, the last two references to Sir 18:1 are extremely simple. In fact, for *simul universam creaturam* and *simul facta est*, only the adverb *simul* coincides in Thiele’s, Weber-Gryson’s, and Sabatier’s editions, thus bringing the percentage of similarity between the Vulgate and the text of Augustine edited by Zycha to 33.33%.

7.2 A Case Study from Greek: Clement of Alexandria’s *Paedagogus*

The expanded classification has been used for the tagging of selected parts of the exegetical works by Clement of Alexandria, as shown above (6.). The aim of this phase of tagging is to create a map of the author’s strategies of reuse of the biblical texts, with a special focus on the reuse of the Pentateuch, both under the linguistic and thematic points of view. The text that has received the WP8 team’s attention first is the *Paedagogus* (M. Harl, H.-I. Marrou, C. Matray, C. Mondésert, Clément d’Alexandrie. *Le pédagogue*, vol. I [Sources Chrétiennes 70], Paris: Éditions du Cerf, 1960). The process of tagging has led the team to expand and deepen the traditional system of reporting intertextual references in Clement’s editions, by highlighting the subtleties of the author’s reuse of biblical texts. Here, two samples of the resulting patterns are shown, based on an initial exploration on the first book of the *Paedagogus*, in which 46 passages have been tagged by the team. The nature of text reuse that

Fig. 6. Apparatus of G_LXX (Num 6:9).

The variant is however only attested in the same author (and the same passage) that is being tagged, so it is omitted in the classification to avoid the circularity of the information. The apparatus also contains the information about a similar variant reading that appears in a work by Philo of Alexandria. The same passage has been tagged by the team during the training period of the platform INCEPTION. The intertextual reference in the text of Philo, *Legum allegoriarum libri III*, 1.17.5, is interesting for our purposes since it is an extremely free rendering of the passage that features the same adjective αἰφνίδιον found in Clement.

The screenshot shows the INCEPTION interface with a document titled 'processed_filone.txt'. The main text area displays a Greek passage with line numbers 221-232. Annotations include 'citazione 1.17.5' and 'citazione 1.18.1'. The sidebar on the right contains a 'Layer' dropdown set to 'Referenze Bibliche', a 'Span' section with 'Deletes' and 'Clear' buttons, a 'Text' input field containing the Greek phrase 'αἰ ἡμέραι αἰ πρότεροι ἄλογοι', and a 'Reference Start' button. The bottom status bar indicates 'Idle' and 'Technische Universität Darmstadt -- Computer Science Department -- INCEPTION -- 29.9 (2023-11-23 18:43:17, build aebfb4d4)'.

Fig. 7. Sample tag from phase zero, showing Philo’s Legum allegoriae, l.17.5.

In conclusion, Clement’s knowledge of the Bible in this case seems to be mediated by the text of Philo, confirming the case for a long-lasting Alexandrian scriptural tradition that leaves traces, although feeble, in the modern edition of the Septuagint. It appears clear that the team’s approach aimed at consistently exploring the Septuagint tradition in its entirety, by means of the two apparatus of the Göttingen edition, proves fruitful in tracing not only the role of Scripture in one author considered on his own, but also on the possible mediation of other authors and the different forms of Scripture through time.

A further example of Clement’s reuse of biblical texts is found at *Paedagogus*, l.3.7 (Fig. 8). Clement is arguing that God loves humankind and draws upon the biblical account of the creation to clarify the human centrality in it. While the other parts of the creation came to be by means of a simple order, in the case of humankind, God made them “with His own hands and blew in them something special”. The text is indicated by Clement’s editors as recalling both Gen 1:26 and 2:7, the two accounts of the creation. The tagging process was thus repeated for the two passages in all available versions. As can be seen in Fig. 8, the literal correspondences are low in both cases (30,43% with Gen 2:7 and 17.39% with Gen 1:26). However, the expanded classification enables the scholar to go deeper in the analysis of similarities, while the overlapping of the tags allows a visualization of how far the two passages are intertwined in Clement’s writing.

Fig. 8. Overlapping tag of Clement’s Paedagogus, l.3.7.

The comparison with Gen 1:26 sees identical tokens, one token from the same lemma (ποιήσωμεν - πεποιήκεν, both from the verb ποιέω, “to make”). The token εἶπεν can be considered a synonym to κελεύων (although the tenses are different, both verbs refer to the act of speaking); the expression ὁ θεός in Clement is in its turn mirrored by the pronoun αὐτοῦ in the biblical text. As far as Gen 2:7 is concerned, the same synonymy has been found between God in Clement and the corresponding pronoun in the biblical text; there is one word in Clement that shares the same root as one in the biblical text, namely πλάσμα and ἔπλασεν. The recensions, whose variants are contained in the second apparatus of G_LXX, either present the same picture (Aquila), or, in the case of Symmachus and Theodotion, have a slight difference with the case ending of the word ἄνθρωπος (the oscillation is between the nominative and the accusative) and two different verbal forms to refer to the vital breath (ἐνεφύσησεν and ἔπνευσεν). This passage highlights how Clement reuses a language that is characteristic of the biblical narratives of creation, without being dependent on one account, but instead composing his own description with reminiscences of both passages. The team has furthermore identified one recall that can fit in the category of *Structure*: the word ἴδιον, “peculiar”, is here the sign of the gift granted to humankind by God in the creation, that is indicated in the biblical text as πνοὴν ζωῆς, “breath of life” (G_LXX) or ἀναπνοὴν ζωῆς (G_σ [Symmachus] and G_θ [Theodotion]). The results of the classification, especially on the *Lemma* and *Root* level, highlight how nuanced and profound Clement’s knowledge of Scripture was and how this deep connection to the words of the book of Genesis allowed the author to consider them as one unit of meaning that could carry the idea of the creation of humankind within a wider discourse functional to his argument.

In conclusion, the classification proves relevant in allowing scholars to highlight the linguistic and thematic nuances of the scriptural reuse in the passages under investigation, providing them with a platform that is open to collaboration, discussion, and deep textual analysis. By taking into account the totality of the available textual materials of both the biblical and the patristic text and by relying on existing scholarly work on intertextuality, the working classification of the WP8 team leads to unexplored (or rarely explored) territories of the tradition, which in turn paves the way to identifying and studying intertextual relationships that may still be obscure to date.

7.3 The Case Study of Arabic: Al-Qurṭubī’s Commentary

A case study that illustrates possible findings on the Arabic corpus is taken from Al-Qurṭubī’s commentary. The work focused on a section of the *al-Ġāmi‘ li Aḥkām al-Qur‘ān* commentary by Abū ‘Abdullāh al-Qurṭubī (d. 1273), specifically the commentary on verse 46:29. The digital version was downloaded from the OpenITI database, and the selected text was revised before being uploaded to INCEPTION for annotation. The annotation allowed for the identification of:

- Quranic verses.
- Passages from Ibn Hišām’s *Sīra al-Nabawīyyah*.

- Intertextual references from collections of *ḥādīṭ* and other *tafāsīr*.

1	سورة الأحقاف (46): آية 29
2	Intertextual Reference Qur'an 100.0 46 29 0 0 وإذ صرفنا إليك نفرا من الجن يستمعون القرآن فلما حضروه قالوا أنصتوا فلما قضي ولأى قومهم منذرين (29)
3	
4	Intertextual Reference Qur'an 100.0 46 29 0 0 Introductory Marker 0.0 0 0 0 0 قوله تعالى : " وإذ صرفنا إليك نفرا من الجن " هذا توبيخ لمشركي قريش، أي إن الجن سمعوا القرآن فأمنوا به وعلمو أنه من عند
5	Intertextual Reference Qur'an 100.0 46 29 0 0 الله وأنتم معرضون مصرون على الكفر. ومعنى "صرفنا" وجهنا إليك وبعثنا. وذلك أنهم صرفوا عن استراق السمع من السماء
6	Intertextual Reference Tafsir 60.53 0 0 Al-Mawardi Al-Nukat al-Uyün 5 285 0 Introductory Marker 0.0 0 0 0 0 برجوم الشهب - على ما يأتي - ولم يكونوا بعد عيسى قد صرفوا عنه إلا عند مبعث النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم. قال المفسرون
7	Intertextual Reference Sira 77.25 0 0 Ibn Hišām Al-Sira al-Nabawiyya 1 1 0 0 Introductory Marker 0.0 0 0 0 0 ابن عباس وسعيد بن جبير ومجاهد وغيرهم: لما مات أبو طالب خرج النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم وحده إلى الطائف يلتمس من
8	Intertextual Reference Sira 77.25 0 0 Ibn Hišām Al-Sira al-Nabawiyya 1 1 0 0 تقيف النصره فقصده عبد ياليل ومسعودا وحبيبا وهم إخوة- بنو عمرو بن عمير- وعندهم امرأة من قريش من بني جمح، فدعاهم إلى
9	Intertextual Reference Sira 77.25 0 0 Ibn Hišām Al-Sira al-Nabawiyya 1 1 0 0 الإيمان وسألهم أن ينصروه على قومه فقال أحدهم: هو يمزط ثياب الكعبة إن كان الله أرسلك! وقال الآخر: ما وجد الله أحدا
10	Intertextual Reference Sira 77.25 0 0 Ibn Hišām Al-Sira al-Nabawiyya 1 1 0 0 يرسله غيرك! وقال الثالث: والله لا أكلمك كلمة أبدا، إن كان الله أرسلك كما تقول فأنت أعظم خطرا من أن أرد عليك الكلام،
11	Intertextual Reference Sira 77.25 0 0 Ibn Hišām Al-Sira al-Nabawiyya 1 1 0 0 وإن كنت تكذب فما ينبغي لي أن أكلمك. ثم أغروا به سفهاءهم وعبيدهم يسيئون ويضحكون به، حتى اجتمع عليه الناس والجنوه إلى

Fig. 9. Examples showing a 60.53% similarity with another commentary and 77.25% similarity from a section of the oldest biography of the prophet.

Intertextual Reference Hadīṭ 0.0 0 0 0 Ibn Hanbal Musnad 4 129 0	
Introductory Marker Hadīṭ 0.0 0 0 0 Muslim Ṣaḥīḥ Kitāb al-Ṣalāḥ 33 0 0	
Intertextual Reference Hadīṭ 0.0 0 0 0 Buḥārī Ṣaḥīḥ Al-ʿAdān 105 0 0	
Intertextual Reference Tafsīr 53.13 0 0 0 Al-Ṭabarī Gāmi' al-bayān 'an ta'wīl āy al-Qur'ān 164 6	
Intertextual Reference Tafsīr 25.0 0 0 0 Al-Ṭabarī Gāmi' al-bayān 'an ta'wīl āy al-Qur'ān 164 1	
Intertextual Reference Tafsīr 28.13 0 0 0 Al-Ṭabarī Gāmi' al-bayān 'an ta'wīl āy al-Qur'ān 21 163 16	
وكان سبب ذلك أنّ الجنّ كانوا يسترقون	
Intertextual Reference Hadīṭ 0.0 0 0 0 Ibn Hanbal Musnad 4 129 0	
Introductory Marker Hadīṭ 0.0 0 0 0 Muslim Ṣaḥīḥ Kitāb al-Ṣalāḥ 33 0 0	
Intertextual Reference Hadīṭ 0.0 0 0 0 Buḥārī Ṣaḥīḥ Al-ʿAdān 105 0 0	
Intertextual Reference Tafsīr 53.13 0 0 0 Al-Ṭabarī Gāmi' al-bayān 'an ta'wīl āy al-Qur'ān 164 6	
Intertextual Reference Tafsīr 25.0 0 0 0 Al-Ṭabarī Gāmi' al-bayān 'an ta'wīl āy al-Qur'ān 164 1	
Intertextual Reference Tafsīr 28.13 0 0 0 Al-Ṭabarī Gāmi' al-bayān 'an ta'wīl āy al-Qur'ān 21 163 16	
السمع، فلما حرست السماء ورموا بالشهب قال إبليس: إنّ هذا الذي حدث في السماء لشيء حدث في الأرض، فبعث سراياه ليعرف	23
Intertextual Reference Hadīṭ 0.0 0 0 0 Ibn Hanbal Musnad 4 129 0	
Introductory Marker Hadīṭ 0.0 0 0 0 Muslim Ṣaḥīḥ Kitāb al-Ṣalāḥ 33 0 0	
Intertextual Reference Hadīṭ 0.0 0 0 0 Buḥārī Ṣaḥīḥ Al-ʿAdān 105 0 0	
Intertextual Reference Tafsīr 53.13 0 0 0 Al-Ṭabarī Gāmi' al-bayān 'an ta'wīl āy al-Qur'ān 164 6	
Intertextual Reference Tafsīr 25.0 0 0 0 Al-Ṭabarī Gāmi' al-bayān 'an ta'wīl āy al-Qur'ān 164 1	
Intertextual Reference Tafsīr 28.13 0 0 0 Al-Ṭabarī Gāmi' al-bayān 'an ta'wīl āy al-Qur'ān 21 163 16	
الخبر، أولهم ركب نصيبين وهم أشرف الجنّ إلى تهامة، فلما بلغوا بطن نخلة سمعوا النبيّ صَلَّى اللهُ عَلَيْهِ وَسَلَّمَ يصلّي صلاة	24
Intertextual Reference Hadīṭ 0.0 0 0 0 Ibn Hanbal Musnad 4 129 0	
Introductory Marker Hadīṭ 0.0 0 0 0 Muslim Ṣaḥīḥ Kitāb al-Ṣalāḥ 33 0 0	
Intertextual Reference Hadīṭ 0.0 0 0 0 Buḥārī Ṣaḥīḥ Al-ʿAdān 105 0 0	
Intertextual Reference Tafsīr 53.13 0 0 0 Al-Ṭabarī Gāmi' al-bayān 'an ta'wīl āy al-Qur'ān 164 6	
Intertextual Reference Tafsīr 25.0 0 0 0 Al-Ṭabarī Gāmi' al-bayān 'an ta'wīl āy al-Qur'ān 164 1	
Intertextual Reference Tafsīr 28.13 0 0 0 Al-Ṭabarī Gāmi' al-bayān 'an ta'wīl āy al-Qur'ān 21 163 16	
الغداة بطن نخلة ويتلو القرآن، فاستمعوا له وقالوا: أنصتوا	25

Fig. 10. Example of detecting a 0% citation, in which a ḥadīṭ from a collection narrates the same episode found in *al-Qurṭubī* without sharing any words.

8. Algorithms and IT Tools

8.1 BERT-Based Models for Latin in Intertextual Analysis of Biblical References

To support the study of biblical references in ancient Christian literature, WP8 investigates the application of BERT-based models for Latin, with a particular focus on the detection of “explicit” citations and “implicit” allusions to biblical texts within patristic commentaries⁵. We tackle this problem as an information retrieval task: given a query, the objective is to retrieve the most relevant documents from a collection. In our settings, a query is a passage from Augustine’s commentary *De Genesi ad litteram*, as described in Sec. 5.2 (see above), and documents are verses from two Latin versions of the Bible (i.e., W_VULG and S_VL: see above, 5.1). Each query is associated with a positive document, corresponding to an intertextual reference between the commentary and the Bible(s). In

⁵ The WP8 team wrote an article concerning the preliminary results of this investigation. It was submitted on December 2024 for 21st *Conference on Information and Research Science Connecting to Digital and Library Science* (IRCDL-The Italian Research Conference on Digital Libraries), 2025, and was accepted with excellent peer reviews: D. CAFFAGNI, F. COCCHI, A. MAMBELLI, F. TUTRONE, M. ZANELLA, M. CORNIA, and R. CUCCHIARA, *Benchmarking BERT-based Models for Latin: A Case Study on Biblical References in Ancient Christian Literature*.

practice, a query may be a literal citation of a biblical verse, or it may just allude to it. The former type of relationship is typically easier to identify by measuring the text overlap between a query and a document. Conversely, allusions to the Bible(s) are hard to detect, as they require complex semantical analysis.

We propose using Transformer-based language models, such as BERT, to effectively capture the complex intertextual references between patristic commentaries and biblical verses. To achieve this, consider a BERT-like pre-trained model. Before processing a query sentence or document, the input is first tokenized. Each token is assigned a unique integer ID, which acts as an index to select the corresponding embedding from the model's input embedding matrix. This sequence of token embeddings is passed through a stack of twelve Transformer layers. The final output is a sequence of embeddings, one for each token in the input.

To generate a single feature vector representing the entire input sequence, we explore two aggregation strategies:

- CLS Token Embedding: BERT-like models prepend a special classification token (CLS) to the input sequence. The output embedding corresponding to the CLS token is commonly regarded as a global representation of the entire input.
- Token Averaging: This strategy involves aggregating information from all tokens in the sequence to create a comprehensive representation by averaging the embeddings of all tokens. Unlike the CLS token approach, which emphasizes a single global summary, token averaging treats each token with equal importance, potentially capturing more detailed information about the input.

To assess the relevance of a document with respect to a query, we compute the cosine similarity between their corresponding embeddings. Cosine similarity measures the angle between two vectors, providing a value that ranges from -1 to 1, where higher values indicate greater similarity. The similarity score is obtained by normalizing both vectors (dividing by their magnitudes) and calculating the dot product.

In our experiments, we use three language models based on the BERT architecture:

- Latin RoBERTa (<https://huggingface.co/pstroe/roberta-base-latin-cased>).
- Latin BERT (<https://github.com/dbamman/latin-bert>).
- LaBERTa (<https://github.com/Heidelberg-NLP/ancient-language-models>).

All the models were pre-trained using a masked language modeling approach, where the model predicts randomly masked words in a given input sentence. The primary distinction between these models lies in the Latin datasets used for pre-training. Latin RoBERTa was trained on 390 million tokens from the Latin portion of CC-100 (<https://paperswithcode.com/dataset/cc100>). Latin BERT

used 642 million tokens gathered from diverse sources, ranging from Classical texts to modern writings. Finally, LaBERTa was trained on 167 million tokens from the *Corpus Corporum* dataset (<https://mlat.uzh.ch/>).

Preliminary experimental results are reported in Table 10. For these experiments, we consider the references from Augustine's commentary annotated by our team and perform retrieval on the two retrieval “*corpora*” composed of biblical verses from two versions of the Latin Bible (i.e., W_VULG and S_VL). Overall, the testing dataset comprises 192 annotated references to the W_VULG Bible and 170 to the S_VL Bible. Retrieval is performed on the two sets of biblical verses, which contain 35,057 verses for W_VULG, but only 20,791 verses for S_VL, due to the unavailability of some original books in digital format. Results are measured using Recall at top- k ($R@k$) for $k \in \{1, 2, 3, 5, 10\}$.

Model	Aggregation	Corpus: W_VULG					Corpus: S_VL				
		R@1	R@2	R@3	R@5	R@10	R@1	R@2	R@3	R@5	R@10
Latin RoBERTa	CLS Token	13.0	13.0	13.5	13.5	14.1	4.7	6.5	8.2	8.2	10.0
Latin RoBERTa	Token Averaging	18.2	20.3	23.4	27.6	30.2	15.9	17.6	18.2	20.6	23.5
Latin BERT	CLS Token	18.2	24.5	26.6	28.1	29.7	18.8	24.1	28.2	32.9	34.1
Latin BERT	Token Averaging	33.3	38.0	41.7	44.8	47.9	35.3	39.4	42.9	45.3	48.8
LaBERTa	CLS Token	31.3	39.1	44.3	47.4	55.7	29.4	34.7	40.0	45.3	50.6
LaBERTa	Token Averaging	34.4	40.6	43.8	47.9	52.6	33.5	37.6	40.0	43.5	47.6

Tab. 10. Performance comparison of existing BERT-based models for Latin on the W_VULG and S_VL corpora, using either the CLS token or the mean of all tokens in the sentence to compute similarities.

As it can be seen, token averaging consistently demonstrates its utility by capturing finer-grained information distributed across all tokens in a sequence, leading to substantial performance improvements for almost all models on both W_VULG and S_VL. Among the three evaluated models, Latin BERT and LaBERTa are the most effective configurations across both biblical versions, achieving the highest recall scores in most scenarios and surpassing the performance of Latin RoBERTa by a consistent margin.

8.2 Parser Development for the *Göttingen Septuagint* Dataset

Regarding the Greek section of WP8, part of the workflow involves the creation of *EnGraSept* (*Enriched Granular Septuagint*), a dataset based on the Göttingen edition of the Septuagint (G_LXX), which includes its textual and Hexaplaric variant readings. In fact, as previously mentioned, WP8, in collaboration with the team of PRIN *Resilient Septuagint*, relies on comparing the works of Christian authors not only with the edited text of the Septuagint but also by considering its textual tradition.

The analysis will be carried out using *Elasticsearch*, a distributed search and analytics engine capable of processing large volumes of data in real time (<https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch>).

However, while XML-OSIS documents containing the edited text of the Göttingen edition — structured into chapters and verses to allow the system to recognize a clear hierarchy— can already be uploaded to *Elasticsearch*, the same cannot be said for the two apparatus. Currently, WP8 only has plain .txt files for this material and, for the machine, these are merely sequences of text lines without any discernible structure or semantic meaning. In order to solve this, WP8 is developing a parser capable of interpreting the .txt format of the Göttingen apparatus and producing structured JSON documents. Specifically, this tool needs to distinguish lemmas, readings, witnesses (from both direct and indirect traditions) and other textual elements such as superscripts, philological notes and abbreviations. Moreover, the parser provides the guidelines to establish a link between each variant and its corresponding lemma in the edited text.

This is being achieved through the creation of a sort of philological dictionary, designed by domain experts, which explains each element of the Göttingen apparatus and includes examples of expected JSON output. For instance, the dictionary defines a “BaseReadingInApparatus” (the lemma) as a series of Greek characters followed by a closing square bracket, while a “ReadingInApparatus” (the reading) is a sequence of Greek characters and words followed by witnesses and ending with a semicolon. The dictionary also clarifies abbreviations such as “om” and “>” (indicating omission) or “+” and “add” (indicating addition). Furthermore, it catalogs and describes all witnesses of direct and indirect traditions for each biblical book. The implementation of this information into the parser is then entrusted to software developers.

The criteria used to define the categories of the apparatus are based on web ontologies, which are conceptual models representing a domain of knowledge through sets of concepts (referred to as “classes”) and their relationships (known as “properties”). A key feature of ontologies is their machine-readable format, which makes them reusable on the Semantic Web, an extension of the World Wide Web that enables computers to interpret and organize data in a standardized manner. Moreover, ontologies allow for the use of a “ubiquitous language”— shared vocabulary between domain experts and developers — aligned with the principles of Data-Driven Design, as articulated by Eric Evans in his seminal work *Domain-Driven Design: Tackling Complexity in the Heart of Software* (2004).

The main ontologies adopted by WP8 are Francesca Giovannetti’s *Critical Apparatus Ontology* (CAO) and Chiara Martignano’s *Critical Edition Ontology* (CEO). Using these, WP8 anticipates that the parser’s output can also be transformed into RDF-OWL, a format that makes the work accessible for the Semantic Web. This requirement aligns with the ITSERR initiative’s mandate to ensure that the resulting knowledge is preserved, remains reusable for scholars, and is machine-readable.

Finally, the JSON produced by the parser will feed another software tool, the Bible Generator. This software must be able to link each *varia lectio* from the apparatus to the Septuagint edited text and automatically generate XML-OSIS virtual versions of the biblical books as they appear in the tradition's witnesses. For instance, given the apparatus entry "1:1 ἐποίησεν] ἔπλασεν 664", the Bible Generator, utilizing the JSON output of the parser, will identify ἔπλασεν as the reading for manuscript 664. Consequently, if the edited text of Genesis begins with Ἐν ἀρχῇ ἐποίησεν ὁ θεὸς τὸν οὐρανὸν καὶ τὴν γῆν, the Bible Generator will produce a version of Genesis for manuscript 664 that reads Ἐν ἀρχῇ ἔπλασεν ὁ θεὸς τὸν οὐρανὸν καὶ τὴν γῆν. The collection of texts from all witnesses will then be integrated into *Elasticsearch*, forming the core dataset of *EnGraSept*.

Encouraged by these promising results, WP8 is also considering a similar workflow for the textual tradition of the Vulgate, based on Weber-Gryson's edition (W_VULG).

8.3 *ElasticSearch* for Indexing and Detecting Biblical References

To address the challenge of identifying references to biblical passages within nonbiblical texts, WP8, in collaboration with *Resilient Septuagint*, employs *ElasticSearch* as a core tool for indexing and querying documents. *ElasticSearch's* powerful search capabilities, combined with tailored preprocessing workflows, enable the system to recognize varying degrees of textual alignment, from direct citations to more nuanced allusions.

Our approach is structured across three distinct but complementary levels of search, each designed to capture a specific dimension of textual similarity.

The first level of analysis focuses on language-agnostic methods, which prioritize word-level alignment without considering linguistic or grammatical nuances. This approach evaluates the shared meaningful terms between texts based on their term frequency-inverse document frequency (TF-IDF) scores. Words that occur frequently across the corpus (e.g., the Greek word καί, meaning "and") are assigned low relevance, while rare and contextually significant terms (e.g., κεχαριτωμένη, uniquely associated with a specific New Testament passage) are assigned higher weights. By leveraging *ElasticSearch's* term statistics, this method ensures robust handling of any language, making it particularly suited for multilingual corpora.

The second level refines the analysis by incorporating language-specific features. Using natural language processing (NLP) tools such as lemmatizers, stemmers, and part-of-speech taggers, the system normalizes text to its base forms and accounts for morphological variations. This step enhances the identification of shared meaning between passages even when synonyms, declensions, or conjugations are present. Furthermore, this level evaluates syntactic structure, comparing the grammatical patterns of two sentences to detect deeper linguistic parallels. For example,

ElasticSearch is extended with custom analyzers tailored to Greek and Latin, allowing it to treat variations like *λόγος* (nominative) and *λόγου* (genitive) as equivalent when appropriate.

The third and most sophisticated level employs semantic similarity through sentence embeddings. This involves transforming entire sentences into high-dimensional vectors using pre-trained language models such as BERT or Sentence-BERT. The vectors capture nuanced meanings and contextual relationships, enabling comparisons based on cosine similarity or other distance metrics. This level excels at detecting indirect allusions, where shared concepts or ideas are present, but explicit word overlap is minimal. For instance, a philosophical reference by Clement of Alexandria to a creation narrative might align semantically with the book of Genesis, even without direct linguistic correspondence.

To provide a unified measure of similarity, the system integrates the results of all three levels into a composite similarity score. Each level is assigned a configurable weight, allowing researchers to emphasize specific dimensions of similarity depending on their analytical goals. For example, direct citations may rely more heavily on language-agnostic scores, while thematic allusions might prioritize semantic embeddings. This flexibility enables dynamic tuning of search parameters to accommodate varying research needs.

The indexed corpus and similarity algorithms empower WP8 to evaluate references within a wide range of texts efficiently. For instance, given a passage from Clement of Alexandria, the system can quickly identify potential parallels in the Septuagint or other biblical sources, offering scholars a ranked list of candidate matches with detailed similarity metrics. These capabilities significantly enhance the study of intertextuality, providing a scalable, adaptable solution for textual analysis in biblical and patristic scholarship.

8.4 FAISS for Indexing and Detecting Sayings of the Prophet

Semantic searches are not limited to biblical references in ancient Greek and Latin commentaries but are also used to search for references to *aḥādīth* in Arabic exegetical texts. From a high-level perspective, the methodology used is closely related to that set up for the search of biblical references: a corpus selected by humanities experts is encoded through a language model to obtain vectorial representations of the text and, in turn, these are used to look for segments that are semantically related to a query.

In this case of a semantic search system, we use AraBERT, an encoder-only language model trained on Arabic texts to transform the corpus into a vectorial representation, and FAISS to create an index of these representations and enable similarity searches.

AraBERT language understanding allows the system to perform semantic based searches that find passages on the basis of their meaning instead of their shape, while the model provides the vectorial representations. Actual searches need a fast similarity search engine. To address this need we deploy FAISS, a high-performance indexing tool, that implements several low-memory and high-speed indexing solutions allowing us to run searches across billions of documents in fractions of a second.

We encode four kinds of documents: *Quran*, *sīra*, *tafāsīr*, and two *ḥādīṭ* collections from the shia and the sunni traditions. This results in a total of 1709972 encoded text chunks. The search interface allows for targeted searches of each individual collection, so that humanities researchers can focus on specific research questions.

The search engine is made available at <https://hadith2text.aimh.cloud.isti.cnr.it/>

9. Conclusions

The methodological framework and preliminary results presented in this whitepaper seem promising for the study of the three *corpora* examined and their traditions. The interaction between the different research fields and expertise involved has led to significant improvements and to the creation of new tools that both support and advance research on the sacred texts of Christianity and Islam and on their commentaries, as well as on intertextual relations within them.

Despite the methodological premises set out above, the taxonomy the WP8 team developed and tested might appear to reduce intertextual relations to a purely quantitative scale and, consequently, to trap the (still largely unknown) potentialities of the human mind of ancient authors in such a scale. Far from attempting to provide a resolution to cognitive problems that, in addition to being highly complex because of the disciplines and sub-disciplines they intertwine, are fundamentally philosophical and still open and debated, it is then useful to remember that the WP8 team's efforts are strictly related to *measurement*. The representation of the textual data considered here aims to move beyond standard classifications that risk becoming dogmatic in the Humanities, such as the polar dichotomy between citation and allusion (based on the principle of the intentionality of the author). The expanded semantic classification displays linguistic and/or thematic similarities between source and target texts, within a historical framework, highlighting the nuanced possibilities of their relations through a spectrum rather than a dichotomy. Likewise, the standard opposition between edited text and variant readings is problematized by integrating the information provided by the critical apparatus into the analysis of intertextual relations.

The WP8 team is thus developing a fresh perspective on the relationship between the Humanities and Computer Science, in an attempt to hold together two models: a model of automatic numerical representation of language, to be trained with similarity classes even at 0%, in the expectation that

someday technology will allow such a *training set* to bear full fruit; and a model in which human input, through an ontology or otherwise “ontologizable” classifications, would be clearly distinguishable in the forms and modes of measurement.

This approach tries to avoid falling back into the vicious circle produced by the nineteenth-century positivist view of the filiation of one text from another (usually one alone), which is regarded as the source. Rather, we take into account the textual plurality of the sacred texts or, more properly, their “granularity”. After all, the strings on which the percentage of similarity is calculated - the target text - are those that transpose and reuse the source: they are the words of the ancient commentaries on the Bibles and the Quran.

Our methodological postulate is well expressed in Umberto Eco’s reflections on his relationship with Borges, which date back to 1997 but are now published in the volume *Sulla letteratura* (Milan 2022, p. 137). Eco managed to summarize - and, on closer inspection, to go beyond - every previous classification system of intertextuality:

One cannot speak of the concept of influence in literature, in philosophy, or even in scientific research, if one does not place an X at the top of the triangle. Shall we call this X the culture, the chain of previous influences? To be consistent with our talk these days, we will call it the *encyclopaedia universe*. [...] The A/B relationship can pose itself in various ways: (1) B finds something in A’s work and does not know that X is behind it; (2) B finds something in A’s work and through A’s work goes back to X; (3) B refers to X and only later realizes that X was in A’s work.

This is the fundamental axiom of WP8 research: the Bible and the Quran, in their own religious and cultural contexts, are the “X”, understood as the material watermark and cultural palimpsest of these ancient worlds and *corpora*. To make a leap of knowledge in these research fields, the sacred and exegetical texts in Ancient Greek, Latin, and Arabic are now being prepared, processed, and explored with the aid of Computer Science, according to solid methodological paradigms of historical and philological axis. The creation of new technological tools in turn incorporates the same knowledge that has produced the research questions of specialists in Religious Studies.

10. Publications

Publications authored by some members of the WP8 team and related to this specific deliverable (D8.1.1) are listed below:

- D. CAFFAGNI, F. COCCHI, A. MAMBELLI, F. TUTRONE, M. ZANELLA, M. CORNIA, and R. CUCCHIARA, *Benchmarking BERT-based Models for Latin: A Case Study on Biblical References in Ancient Christian Literature*, in *Proceedings of the 21st Conference on Information and Research Science*

Connecting to Digital and Library Science (February 20-21, 2025, Udine, Italy), 2025, forthcoming.

- D. DAINESE, and A. MAMBELLI, *Intertestualità tra Bibbie e antichi commentari cristiani: l'esempio di simul nel De Genesi ad litteram di Agostino*, in "Lexicon Philosophicum: International Journal for the History of Texts and Ideas", 11 (2023–2024), pp. 39-65.
Open Access: <https://lexicon.cnr.it/ojs/index.php/LP/article/view/872/726>
- A. MAMBELLI, «Verranno giorni...» nel Vangelo di Luca: *l'influenza di Geremia LXX sulle profezie di Gesù riguardanti la distruzione di Gerusalemme*, in A. MAMBELLI (ed.) "And from the daughter of Zion all her beauty is departed" (Lam 1:6). *Reactions, Responses, and Reflections on the Fall of Jerusalem from the 1st to the 4th Century CE*, monographic section of "Annali di Storia dell'Esegesi", 41, 2 (2024), pp. 275-310.
- F. TUTRONE, *Aëriae Animae: Souls and Elements from the Roman Cosmos to the Christian Afterworld*, in M. Cesario, H. Magennis, and E. Ramazzina (eds.), *An Interdisciplinary Study of the Elements*, Vol. 3: *Air*, Leiden: Brill, 2025, forthcoming.
- F. TUTRONE, *Dreams, Texts, and Truths: Augustine on Hermeneutics and Oneirocriticism*, in P. Montanari (ed.), *Approaching Meaning: Background, Difference, Mind and the Hermeneutics of Ancient Texts. Essays in Memory of David Konstan*, Berlin-Boston: De Gruyter, 2025, forthcoming.

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